

THE STRUCTURE OF CIVIL CONFLICT

A FIRST STEP TO COMPUTER ASSISTED DISPUTE RESOLUTION

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I INTRODUCTION

Conflict performs a social function, although its effects are often considered disadvantageous to society. That perception is arguably a matter of perspective and degree, rather than an objective assessment. Just as war can be seen as the continuation of politics by other means (Clausewitz, 1873),¹ conflict can be seen as a form of communication to which different rules of engagement apply, and where the purpose of the exchange takes on another character. To use another quote from Clausewitz:

"War is an act of force to compel our enemy to do our will."

It is proposed that this accurately indicates the difference between conflict and ordinary negotiation or communication, and provides a good starting point for a paper about civil conflict.

Although the word conflict has negative connotations, conflict situations can create an environment for superior achievement, ultimately leading to positive results. The negative aspects are associated with those conflicts where the efforts expended on sustaining the conflict itself and the associated emotional and societal costs outweigh the substantive benefits.

This paper argues that a successful society or organisation has effective means of managing conflict in such a way that the positive effects can be maintained, while the negative effects are avoided or minimised. The use of independent third parties ("neutrals") to determine a dispute or to assist the parties to resolve it is one of the ways in which conflict can be managed. More or less formal mechanisms for dispute resolution develop as a society becomes more complicated. The court system is the prime example of an institu-

¹ "It is of course well known that the only source of war is politics -- the intercourse of governments and peoples. We maintain that war is simply a continuation of political intercourse, with the addition of other means."

tionalised and formal mechanism. It may be seen as the pinnacle of development of structured conflict resolution, but is by no means the only process available to disputing parties. An array of “alternative” mechanisms to obtain assistance in resolving conflict exists. These mechanisms are normally referred to as “Alternative Dispute Resolution” (ADR), and are often broadly categorised into negotiation, mediation and arbitration. The characterising difference between the court- and ADR processes is that the former allows a party to involve the other in a procedure against it will. Court processes provide a means of determining a dispute by means of methods that are sanctioned and supported by the state. Consequently, such methods have to include strict procedural safeguards to avoid abuse. These procedural safeguards result in a level of formality that makes court procedures somewhat cumbersome and consequently inefficient and expensive. ADR methods require voluntary acceptance to participate in a procedure, given before or after the dispute arises. Hence, ADR processes attract the description “consensual” dispute resolution. It must be noted that that sharp distinction is being “blurred” increasingly by legislation and rules that seek to include ‘consensual’ procedures into formal court proceedings, or even to use them as an alternative. Examples may be found in areas of employment, construction and family law. A recent development in New Zealand can be found in new District Court rules that are under development, and which will include an obligatory judicial settlement conference, very early after the start of the procedure.² Such developments are driven by the recognition that court proceedings have disadvantages that may be avoided by ADR processes. Costs and efficiency are examples. A persuasive argument for the ‘meditative’ ADR procedures is that declaring a winner at the end of litigation (or arbitration) may be an end to a dispute, but this does not necessarily equal ‘resolution’. Opportunities to resolve the dispute in more advantageous ways for

² (District Court Claims Sub-committee, 2004, 2005)

both parties may have been missed as a result of the focus on ‘winning versus losing’ that is inevitable in the way adjudicative procedures operate.

A recent study investigated the way in which ADR techniques³ are used as part of, or as an alternative to, traditional civil litigation in New Zealand (Saville-Smith, 2004). It found an awareness and acceptance of alternative techniques, and recognition that these techniques require a different infrastructure and approach than traditional court procedures. Unawareness and a lack of understanding of ADR among disputants and lawyers were found to be the mayor inhibitor of improved ADR take-up in New Zealand. The study did not identify the similarities and differences between court process and alternative techniques, and their impact on the acceptance of ADR.

Another conclusion of the study is that the public is generally not aware of civil court procedure, especially about the rules relating to information exchange between the parties once litigation has started. It further found that the optimal point to use a consensual resolution process is after the discovery and other interlocutory stages have been completed, i.e. once the parties have disclosed all information relevant to the dispute. This is also the point where judicial settlement conferences normally take place. Interestingly, it found that the judiciary do not consider such conferences a form of ADR. A further conclusion was that the majority of litigants that used a consensual process to resolve the dispute before it proceeded to a hearing were satisfied with the outcome, while the majority of litigants that completed the litigation were not.⁴ It would seem that a formalised information exchange; followed by a consensual resolution process is a satisfactory way to resolve conflict.

³ By which the report referred to the mediation-type procedures.

⁴ Which conclusion was similar to that in an Australian study (Delaney & Wright, 1997).

The initiative in New Zealand to introduce entirely new rules to initiate civil proceedings comes as recognition of those conclusions, and the proposed District Court rules are characterised by a strong focus on information exchange, followed by an early judicial settlement conference, which, if unsuccessful, becomes a first conference in which procedural matters for the proceedings are determined. A trial with such rules in one District Court registry demonstrated that 23% of the cases settled before the conference, apparently as a result of information exchange; and a further 43% settled during or shortly after the conference. In all, a settlement rate of 66%.⁵

Different dispute resolution or adjudication processes deal with information in different ways. This relates to the type of information used and to what use it can be put, how the exchange of information between parties and the neutral is organised, and what the role of the neutral is in resolving the conflict. This paper proposes that the use of information is a commonality between dispute resolution processes, but that the way information is used is one of the defining differences between these processes. No research has been found that compares or coordinates information exchange processes between different conflict resolution methods.

Information exchange, or the lack of it, also plays a vital role in the origin and development of conflict. Even major international crises would not have taken place if the conflicting parties would have had means to effectively exchange objective information. The Cuba missile crisis is a case in point; shortly after the crisis the famous “hot line” between the American and Russian presidents was installed.⁶

This paper is concerned with the role of information exchange in conflict. Information exchange is a central feature in the way con-

⁵ Although the sample was quite small. (District Court Claims Sub-committee, 2004, 2005)

flict originates, how it develops, is sustained, and how conflict is eventually terminated or resolved. Court procedures and the formal ADR techniques such as arbitration have some way of standardising information exchange. There is a correlation between the degree of formality of information exchange and the adjudicative character of the dispute resolution process. Less formal resolution techniques, such as mediation have no standardised or structured information exchange processes. It is left to the neutral to organise these matters, if at all. As a result, conflicting parties that seek to resolve a dispute through various mechanisms (e.g. negotiation, mediation, expert determination and finally a court procedure), may be confronted with different, and conflicting, information exchange processes.

This paper proposes that improving and formalising information exchange about substantive issues in conflict (as parties are eventually forced to do in a court procedure), will prevent escalation of conflict and assist in resolution of disputes.

If information exchange has the vital role that is proposed, developments in information technology will have an impact on the way conflict resolution can be undertaken. The focus of this paper is on the potential use of information technology in dispute resolution. It is not concerned with using existing technology such as email or word-processing, or even litigation support systems but with the use of technology to provide an alternative dispute resolution environment in its own right. It seeks to achieve that purpose by looking at the structure of conflict and the role of information exchange in it.

This research paper is intended to be part of a larger project of post-graduate research. The ultimate aim is to produce an automated information system or infrastructure, which can support parties, their advisors and neutral facilitators or adjudicators in the resolution or determination of civil disputes. This system can be conceptualised

⁶ See for example http://www.jfklibrary.org/cmc_exhibit_2002.html

as an alternative to other dispute resolution processes, or as an infrastructure supporting these, the distinction is not considered relevant at this point.

Information exchange is presented as the commonality between dispute resolution techniques, yet those techniques use the same information in a different way, and require different standards of information “quality”. Consequently, an information exchange system should be ‘transparent’ to the character of the resolution process in which it is used. It should support any dispute resolution process, from the most formal such as litigation and arbitration, to the less formal such as mediation, and even the entirely unstructured processes, such as negotiation between the parties. It should also be able to provide for a seamless transition from one resolution process to another, in the situation where a dispute in which it is used, requires such a transition. In the remainder of this report this conceptual system is termed the ‘CADR’ system, which stands for “Computer Assisted Dispute Resolution”.

This development project will have three phases: first the development of the theoretical basis and models of conflict, secondly the description of the CADR system with its processes and data structures, and finally the actual development of the system and a user interface.

It is envisaged that the first phase of the project, the development of a model of conflict, will complete the requirements for this 50-point Master’s degree research paper. The author hopes to complete the second stage of the project in the course of further post-graduate study. The realisation of the third stage will depend not only on the results of the first two stages, but also on the commercial realities related to the development of complex information systems.

This paper first describes the context in which the idea was formed to research this particular topic, and the reasons behind the

approach that has been chosen. It then sets out the main propositions forming the foundation of the conflict model that is constructed. That model will eventually be the structural ‘skeleton’ for the functionality of the CADR system. Although this paper does not extend into the further stages of the project, the current conceptual ideas for the CADR system are briefly discussed, in order to provide some context.

The description of a conflict-model is the entire scope of this first stage of the research project. To provide a descriptive title for this paper, this stage has been termed:

“THE STRUCTURE OF CIVIL CONFLICT:

A first step to Computer Assisted Dispute Resolution”.

When the author found that conflict theory, rather than ADR theory could provide the basis for understanding the structure of conflict resolution, it became clear that an overview of conflict theory and its assumptions was necessary to provide the context for the development of the models for this part of the CADR project. As a result brief descriptions of some elementary concepts of conflict theory are provided. It is hoped that this will assist in understanding the description of the components of the models that are presented in this study.

It is theorised that the concepts and developments of the “semantic web”⁷ will provide a useable environment for the development of a CADR system. Therefore, eventually the components and interactions in the model will have to be transformed into ‘ontology’ of conflict within the appropriate syntax specifications for that environment.⁸ It is further expected that developments surrounding the “semantic web”, such as metadata extraction tools and back-end

⁷ For an introduction to the semantic web see (Berners-Lee, Hendler, & Lassila, 2001) and also www.w3.org/2001/sw/

search languages will provide tools that can be used in a CADR system. In order to maximise the potential to integrate such tools in the system it is necessary to adopt the concepts and standards on which the “semantic web” is based. This consideration provides both direction and restrictions.

Automated systems to support conflict resolution are a recent development (Conley Tyler & Bretherton, 2003). Initially those systems will be seen as an extension of the role of the third party, but they can readily assume the role of “fourth party”, and it has been argued that, with the advance of on-line dispute resolution, and the consequential possibilities of ‘forum-shopping’ they might evolve into “fifth parties”, which has interesting consequences for the potential liabilities of suppliers of resolution services (Bol, 2005).

It has also been argued that professional development of ADR, especially mediation, has reached a critical phase, which comprises the transition from conception to real acceptance (Mayer, 2004). Use of technology to structure and support the information exchange that is an essential part of conflict resolution, may help to standardise and make resolution processes more understandable and accessible. This could eventually help ADR to make the transition from the somewhat misunderstood relative of judicial procedure to a mainstream means to resolve differences.

⁸ Which will likely be some future development onto RDF/XML, see further <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-syntax-grammar/>

II CONTEXT

A. *PROVISO*

Conflict comes in many varieties, shapes and sizes. What all types of conflict have in common is the requirement that there must be two or more parties that have an expressed struggle resulting from the perception that they have interdependent goals. It is also necessary that there is a substantial emotional aspect, which distinguishes conflict from simple negotiation. Some restrictions have been made that reduce the scope of this research paper to specific types of conflict.

First, this project is limited to conflicts between two parties. The main reason for that approach is that this two-party concept underlies all of the existing dispute resolution systems, and is the basis of most research. Other actors however always play roles in the ‘environment’ of the principal parties. This is a factor that will have to be addressed. It has not been conceptualised whether multi party conflicts can be seen as a construct of a number of two party-conflicts in which further parties are influencing actors, or whether there is something fundamentally different in multi party conflicts. This question is not addressed in this paper, and consequently multi party disputes are excluded.

Secondly, the project is limited to conflict situations where the scope of the dispute is one that can normally be dealt with in the court system. This restriction excludes conflicts between nations, or political conflicts. The system that is envisaged is also focussed on what is normally called civil conflict, thereby excluding those disputes that, in the legal system, are included in areas such as criminal or administrative law or matters concerning human rights. The background of this exclusion is the focus on disputes with discerna-

ble parties, operating in a societal environment. Conflicts between individuals and society itself, which are at issue in the excluded types of disputes, have a very different nature which has not been considered.

Thirdly, the project is mainly aimed at conflicts that include substantive and material issues. Conflicts that consist solely of emotional issues are not considered. The background for this exclusion lies in the approach that has been chosen, which seeks to disconnect emotional from substantive issues in conflict as a means of restoring information exchange between parties. Disputes that only deal with emotional issues⁹ do not provide that opportunity and have to be excluded for that reason. As will be seen, relationship issues will be described as ‘substantial’ if they include observable and measurable parameters.¹⁰ Disputes about relationships, such as those in the family law environment, can therefore be included in the approach that is proposed in this paper. Although these disputes are characterised by a large emotive content, objectives and outcomes are described in substantive terms, whether these are relationship parameters or more substantial issues such as the division of property.

The justification for the exclusions described above is found in the purpose of this project. It ultimately has a practical goal, and therefore has a ‘strategic research’ character, which allows exclusion of related but not directly relevant material.

B. PROPOSITIONS

The inspiration behind this project is the result of a number of observations and assumptions, which are discussed in this paper, and which can be summarised in the following propositions:

⁹ Religious disputes would be an example.

¹⁰ Which must logically be the case, otherwise a court determination would be impossible.

- Social behaviour requires organisation, which requires communication and arrangements between participants in social processes. These social actors (which will be called ‘agents’ in this paper, can eventually end up as parties to a conflict, where the arrangements between them have not operated in the way they were intended.
- Communication between parties contains information exchange on substantive, relationship, and procedural topics.
- Entirely rational (i.e. non emotional) parties would always be able to negotiate a resolution for any difference about substantive issues, if they have the appropriate procedural environment available to achieve disclosure and exchange of perfect information.
- Conflict is a form of communication, in which emotional issues have attained a disproportional role, which frustrates the information exchange that is necessary to resolve substantive issues.
- Conflict is ultimately aimed at reorganisation of resources and relationships.
- Emotional issues are the result of the (ab)use of ‘power’ characteristics in the underlying relationship between the parties.
- If parties are assisted to recognise the differences and relationships between substantive and relational objectives, more options to generate resolution alternatives will become available.
- Increasing the agreement on the objective facts underlying the dispute increases the chance of resolution between the parties.
- Increased understanding of conflict resolution mechanisms and the related costs and efforts increases the parties’ motivation to resolve conflict.
- Most dispute resolution processes rely on (temporarily) restoring information exchange on substantive, rather than emotional issues. This is achieved by placing emphasis on procedural requirements, which also seek to achieve “completeness” of information exchange.
- Information technology can be used to improve information exchange, and can be used as a ‘filter’ to separate substantive and emotional content, and may provide an environment with a ‘climate’ suitable to exchange infor-

mation on relationship issues, with reduced risk of conflict escalation.

- Language is the carrier of conflict communication. Semantic analysis can recognise patterns of conflict communication and separate and evaluate emotional and substantive content.
- If the structure of conflict and conflict language can be understood, this analysis and evaluation can be automated, and performed by means of ‘artificial intelligence’.
- Communication and conflict models can be used to represent and understand conflict development and escalation.
- Conflict can be represented by using static and dynamic models. Although these distinct modelling techniques can be used to analyse and study different aspects of conflict, integration of static and dynamic models is necessary.

Somewhat surprisingly, the use of modern information technology to avert or resolve conflict does not seem to keep pace with the speed in which information technology creates or complicates conflict. Court proceedings in information rich procedures provide good examples where hundreds of thousands of computer generated documents are transformed into paper format in order to be used in court, causing substantial logistical problems. A related development (and complication) is found in the documentary possibilities of modern information technology. Much more information is retained and retrievable than used to be the case. The use of inter-company email memoranda in anti-competition cases provides a good example. Another relevant development is the informality connected with the use of technology to exchange information. An increasing volume of documented communication is generated, which may eventually have an impact well outside of what was intended. Sloppy thinking, careless use of language, and the presumption that material is non-discoverable, may be provided as an explanation. Examples are email and chat room environments, and the increasing use of text

messaging devices that register and store data. Another related development is the acceptance of communication technologies to engage in information exchange of a personal nature. Matters that were traditionally kept in spheres of absolute privacy, are now submitted to environments where privacy and anonymity are only perceived values, and where the average user has no idea to what extent his communications are recorded, stored and made accessible and/or retrievable. Additionally, recorded information, even if it is of a strictly informal nature such as a chat message, an impromptu email or even a recorded phone message, may attract an evidential value that is disproportionate to the intention with which such a communication was made. The informality of modern communication methods increases ambiguity and the possibility of misunderstanding. In conclusion, information technology is certainly playing a role in increasing the scope and complexity of conflict.

On the other side of the equation, improvement in information exchange possibilities could theoretically reduce the possibility of conflict, as misunderstandings can be prevented or resolved. Similarly, the adjudication mechanisms in society can also be equipped with the new communication and information exchange infrastructure, which can lead to a dramatic reduction of processing time, and a proportionate increase in counsel's efficiency and the courts' capacity to process disputes. As a result, a reduction in litigation costs would be expected. This is not the case. Litigation costs are forever increasing, and it appears that they have risen sharply over the last years. Although information technology is used increasingly, this is primarily in areas and applications of a "general" character, such as office automation systems, applications for document management, project management etc. Introduction of technology in the primary processes of conflict resolution is limited. A brief research of litigation support systems reveals a dramatic increase in capabilities to handle large volumes of documents and data, and attempts to organ-

ise information in a way that follows the structure of legal reasoning, especially the presentation of evidence. On-line dispute resolution is largely limited to blind-bidding systems or the use of communication technology to exchange information with the neutral assisting in the dispute resolution.

The increasing use of information technology to streamline and enhance the capacity of formal adjudication processes appears to be outdone by the increase in the amount of documents and data and the complexity of disputes that are generated by the disputants in an increasingly litigious society.

In conclusion, the growing complexity of society, and the impact of new technology can be a source of, or complication of conflict, while the potential for use of new technology in conflict resolution appears to lag somewhat behind. As with all new technology, its virtues tend to be exaggerated, while less favourable characteristics are suppressed. Rapid development is usually followed by regulation until some equilibrium is reached. The state of affairs at this point appears to be that modern information technology plays a role in increasing the scope and complexity of conflict, but is not used with a proportional increase to avoid or resolve conflict.¹¹ A strong increase in the use of information technology to resolve conflict may therefore be expected, with the initial focus on the determination how this can be achieved.

This conclusion has sparked the desire to investigate if the advances in technology can be used to restore or repair the information exchange problems that go hand in hand with the development and escalation of conflict. It is a natural reaction to restrict or formalise information exchange when conflict arises, and to use what remains

¹¹ Whereby it must be remarked that there is a substantial area of disputes that are the result of technology (disputes arising between international parties to e-auction transactions), that is resolved within the technological environment in which they arise.

for conflict dynamics rather than for substantive information exchange. Information and communication technology does not, and cannot change that instinctive reaction by itself. What it can do however, and what is not available in more traditional means of communication, is to add an interface, which provides some 'intelligence' between communicators and their messages.

Essentially this is what happens in any dispute resolution process, especially where third parties become involved. The communication environment and procedures are changed in such a way that the parties are restricted in the type of information they can exchange between themselves and with the third party, and the way they can do that. The purpose is to prevent further escalation of conflict, and to focus on communication that is helpful to resolve or determine the issues, rather than complicate them further. If it is understood what type of information exchange escalates conflict and what type is helpful to resolve it, and if there are means to make an automated system that can distinguish between the two, there is no reason why an automated system would not be able to provide an environment that focuses on information that resolves, rather than sustains or escalates conflict. Such a system must be capable of analysing conflict information and of determining how to classify it. Semantic analysis is suggested as a means to achieve that, although the state of the art in automated semantic analysis is not advanced enough to successfully do that. A practical target must be set, somewhere between what is available at the moment, and what can be conceptualised.

What is proposed is the possibility to create an information collection and exchange environment, specifically aimed at dispute resolution or determination. This would take place by focussing the information *exchange* on substantive rather than emotional issues and improving the quality of that exchange. The information *collection and registration* must include the emotional component of con-

flict, which can be used to resolve the conflict about the substantive issues.

Generally speaking, the construction of information systems involves analysis of processes and data-structures. An information system developer will require a thorough understanding of what an information system is supposed to do (the process), and what sort of information it must contain (the data-structure). The analysis and definition of the system can be approached from the perspective of the process or from that of the data-structure. The end result will be a combined description of both, together with a description of a user-interface and a number of secondary matters such as the system distribution, maintenance, security and so on.

As the substance of conflict and the way conflict evolves contain many variables in an endless variety of configurations, it is unlikely that data-structures will be found that are common to all conflicts and conflict resolution processes. It therefore appears sensible to start with an understanding of the process itself. For the formal processes, such as arbitration and litigation that is reasonably clear, but exactly what happens in the “alternative” processes, such as mediation is not as obvious. What information is exchanged, how, and why? What does the neutral do with that information, how is it organised, classified, and processed? Can the process be divided in logical steps, how do those steps relate to one another, what information is used at each step, and how does it flow from one part of the process to the next? How are the sub-processes delineated and why, what does the terminology mean, and how is it related to the process and the information? These and many more questions must be answered in order to create an information system to support such an alternative resolution process.

It was therefore theorised that study of alternative dispute resolution would provide an insight in the structure of the various ADR

processes, from which an understanding of dispute resolution communication (information exchange) would follow. This understanding could then form the basis for the development of a CADR system. At issue is therefore the structure of dispute resolution. Before that can be addressed it is necessary to say something about the different ADR processes and the concept of justice.

C. *ADR AND THE CONCEPT OF JUSTICE*

Alternative dispute resolution is a somewhat ambiguous term. The word “alternative” can be understood to mean that it provides an alternative to the court process,¹² or that it provides a process that is itself ‘alternative’.¹³ As will be seen, both meanings apply. To complicate matters, the abbreviation ADR is also sometimes interpreted to mean “assisted dispute resolution” or “advisory dispute resolution”, or other terms that fit within the general abbreviation.¹⁴ Alternative dispute resolution is a generic term for an ever increasing range of processes, described with a developing terminology, and including such terms as mediation, facilitation, narrative mediation, principled negotiation, arbitration, Med-Arb etc.

This terminology has, upon closer scrutiny, an ambiguous flexibility to it, making it somewhat elusive to define what one is actually talking about. The real ‘alternative’ methods are those that seek to ‘empower’ the parties to a dispute thereby creating novel ways of assisted communication. To use a blatant oversimplification, this assisted communication process helps and guides the parties to rearrange the interests that underlie the issues between them to a more acceptable constellation for both, or assists them in changing the way

¹² And including procedures such as arbitration, that closely mimic court procedure.

¹³ And including procedures that relate closely to counselling and therapy.

¹⁴ And even the term “automated dispute resolution” is found (NADRAC, 2003b).

they perceive the issues, resulting in the realisation that what looked like a dispute really isn't one.

Using this over-simplification, there is some apparent logic to alternative dispute resolution, but when the question arises how this is to be achieved in detail, the answer is less straightforward. There appear to be as many approaches as there are authors of texts, and the terminology has not yet achieved a level of standardisation, that would be helpful for the aspiring information system developer in search of an understanding of the different processes involved.¹⁵

The best way to approach a description of alternative dispute resolution is by realising that there is a "continuum"¹⁶ starting with negotiation between the parties, and ending with arbitration, which is a consensual and privatised, but nevertheless close relative of formal litigation. In between these extremes are other procedures with different characteristics. A way of understanding the differences between ADR processes is proposed by Boule (Boule, Jones, & Goldblatt, 1998), who represents the extremes of a number of characteristic of the (mediation) process by means of "sliding buttons" on a "mediation abacus", with each resulting configuration representing a different resolution process. This abacus is represented in the diagram that follows.

¹⁵ Although there are certainly attempts to come to some standardisation of terms see as an example (NADRAC, 2003b).

¹⁶ Moore (Moore, 2003) describes a continuum from avoidance to violence, characterised by increase of coercion and the occurrence of win-lose outcomes. ADR represents a segment of this continuum.

Figure 1 The mediation abacus

Although this is understandable and helpful for those involved in the ADR profession, it certainly does not make matters simpler to understand for the average “consumer” of ADR services, or for the aspiring system developer that has been introduced above. The way information exchange is organised, or the way information is qualified is not specifically included in the ‘abacus’ representation, although most of the characteristics have a direct impact on information exchange.

The ADR “continuum” contains two important ‘bars’, at which point a significant change of process takes place. The first is located at the point where an outsider (the ‘neutral’) is introduced to assist the parties. The second is at the point where the responsibility for decision making shifts from the parties to the neutral. Both points also signify important changes in the information exchange process, in the type of information that will be exchanged, the quality of information, and the way it is used.

Despite the ambiguity in what is exactly meant by ‘alternative dispute resolution’ the ADR movement has caught on, assisted by strong government support, especially in the common law jurisdictions. The acceptance of ADR in the common law world may be related to the problems associated with the adversarial context of the court procedures in that system. This adversarial approach tends to focus on winning versus losing, rather than on achieving an outcome which is acceptable for both parties. In that context ADR provides a real alternative to the available court procedures.

ADR programmes are blossoming, and are actively used to (more or less successfully) channel whole areas of new and old disputes out of the more formal jurisdictions. Limited information is available on the performance or exact operation of these programmes in New Zealand.¹⁷ As most of the ADR processes operate in an environment of strict confidentiality, it is hard to obtain information on what is actually going on behind the ADR doors. What can be observed is in- and output, but how the “black box” operates must be mostly gleaned from secondary sources, such as the literature produced by researchers in the field (often practitioners), and “after the fact” information from parties and practitioners (Saville-Smith,

¹⁷ In Australia a comprehensive study was undertaken in 2003, but which lacks comparative data with other years or with the formal (litigation) procedures (NADRAC, 2003a).

2004). The amount of information available from direct observation is limited; there is hardly any case law.¹⁸

The lack in standardisation of terminology,¹⁹ and the tendency to “prophesise”, which is characteristic of developers of most new areas of professionalism,²⁰ makes it difficult to really compare and synthesise from the materials that are available (Saville-Smith, 2004)²¹. In other words, a clear understanding, such as one might obtain from less ‘practical’ and more ‘theoretical’ studies cannot be gathered from a study in ADR. If one would have to characterise the field it could be placed somewhere between sociology, social psychology, counselling, management and law, depending on which ADR processes one is describing. Added to the mix is often a dose of knowledge of the subject matter of the dispute as well, especially in specialised fields of ADR, as in share-milking disputes, construction adjudication, real estate and rental disputes, employment mediation etc. This could complicate an attempt to understand the actual ADR process involved, as the participants and the neutral are communicating from the perspective of some common expertise in that subject matter, which confuses the distinction between communication process and content.

It is obvious however, that ADR is not just an alternative to the court process. It is indeed an alternative process as well, providing many potential advantages. Court processes are highly regulated and

¹⁸ With the exception of some formalized ADR systems, such as the WIPO domain name dispute resolution system, which is very specialized and highly structured in process.

¹⁹ For an example of a government assisted effort to come to a standardisation of ADR terminology see (NADRAC, 2003b).

²⁰ An interesting characterisation of mediation professionals is included in the following quote: “In the stormy ocean of conflict, mediation is proving to be a fragile vessel with a hardy crew” (Boulle *et al.*, 1998).

²¹ In this report it was found that ADR practitioners have by far the highest confidence in the value of ADR, as compared to lawyers (who considered lawyer achieved settlements more successful), the judiciary (who considered settlement conferences the preferred option), and litigants (who are generally not impressed with anything).

prearranged, which has historical and practical backgrounds resulting from considerations of natural justice. Most ADR processes lack a fixed structure as that is thought to impede on the necessary flexibility to create the environment in which the parties can be properly empowered. It is apparently considered that overly formal systems of information exchange restrict an efficient approach to resolution of disputes. It is no surprise to find that the first victim of attempts at 'accessibility to justice' is always the formality of the process.

A good example of that principle in operation is the introduction in New Zealand of 'dispute tribunals', where small claims are decided in a semi-formal setting, from which lawyers are excluded, and minimal formality is used. The rules of evidence and procedural safe guards are removed to obtain efficiency. Information exchange prior to a hearing is limited to what parties wish to provide and the referee (the government appointed third party neutral) has very limited, or no powers to order discovery or anything of that nature. The way dispute tribunals operate can be best described in ADR terminology as a form of "Med-Arb". The parties are invited to present their side of the story to the referee, who will in first instance attempt to 'mediate' the dispute, but who will decide the matter when that attempt fails. The process is non-consensual in the sense that the plaintiff (who is called the applicant), is likely to succeed in its case when the defendant (called the respondent) refuses to participate, unless the case is patently hopeless. The coercion of a court procedure is therefore available, but without the right to representation and the other procedural safeguards of court proceedings, which are considered "formal stumbling blocks" to this "common sense justice":²²

"The preference for harmony over conflict, for mechanisms that offer equal access to the many rather than unequal privilege to the few, that operate quickly and cheaply, that permit all citizens to participate in decision mak-

²² Abel, R.L. *The Politics of informal justice*, 1982, Academic Press, Vol1, as quoted in Spiller. (Spiller, 2003).

ing rather than limiting authority to the ‘professionals’, that are familiar rather than esoteric, and that strive for and achieve substantive justice rather than frustrating it in the name of form.”

The type of dispute that can be brought before these tribunals is restricted, as is the amount of money involved, but the financial limit is such that most ‘litigants’ would consider it more than substantial. The referees are not required to have a legal background, but provide a decision that is enforceable in court. Hearings take place in court premises and the administrative organisation is catered for by the court’s registries. The tribunals certainly provide a well-used service, and they are considered a success (Spiller, 2003). Yet one could argue that as a result of the process used, they in fact represent second-rate justice for those that cannot afford access to the “real” courts.

Additionally, observation of civil court proceedings may lead to some scepticism about the way justice operates in practice as well. A first observation is that complex factual information is condensed by (over-) simplification in order to allow application of the legal principles necessary to reach a decision. Another observation relates to the way seemingly unimportant details can obtain a disproportionate relevance, as a result of the “dynamics” of a hearing, especially in adversarial circumstances. Apparently this is the result of the accepted conception that advocacy is all about ‘presenting’ the case to the court (Robertson & Eichelbaum, 2000). What will be presented to the court, how this is done and why, is left to the advocates, who will make a selection and decision based on uncertain criteria, even including the character of the judge! It can be concluded that the information exchange in court procedures has the inherent risk of failing to make it clear to the court what exactly the relevant issues are on which a determination is sought, or how the facts relate to them. It must also be noted that reading case law does not provide any insight in what the parties themselves actually considered what

their dispute was about. Observations in court itself and perusal of pleadings and other documents often paint a different picture than that emerges from the reported decision. It must be realised that a reported decision is produced at a point where at least three or four “translations” of the actual dispute have taken place. The disputant will have explained matters to a solicitor, who will have instructed a barrister, who has presented matters to the court, and eventually the court produces its findings and conclusions. The situation is not incomparable with the “Chinese whispers” game. Although no detailed research into this phenomenon has been found, it is theorised that the dissatisfaction of litigants with civil court procedure (Delaney *et al.*, 1997; Saville-Smith, 2004) may be related to this observation.

In 2004 the New Zealand Law Commission issued a report “Delivering justice for all” (NZLC, 2004), which discusses the problems with efficiency and effectiveness in delivering justice, and how increased case loads and costs are impediments to access to justice.

An international study into the way justice and efficiency relate, includes the following conclusions, which are relevant for the alternative role of ADR, and the subject of this paper (Fix Fierro, 2003):²³

- The process for reaching legal decisions has a value of its own for participants, independent from the value (efficiency) of the outcome for such participants. If litigation is not fair, citizens will have little incentive to use the courts, regardless of how efficient the outcome may be.
- Justice is not a market, but there is a (restricted) market for justice. Demand will seldom reach a state of equilibrium with respect to the supply of judicial services. Gains in court efficiency will always therefore be temporary.

²³ The summary conclusions here are taken from a book review: Rachel Hayward, “Courts justice and efficiency” NZLJ, Feb 2005, pg 29.

- ADR is not necessarily cheaper and speedier than ordinary adjudication; it may both reduce and increase costs. However, it has a critical role to play in helping and regulating the demand of, and the supply of judicial services.

In conclusion, there appears to be a relationship between the “quality of justice” and the efficiency with which it can be provided.

It must be realised that “justice” is a perceived social construct, which does not possess an absolute normative value, and which defies accurate definition. In a diversified and plural society it is unlikely that common ground will exist about what is “just” and what not. There is ambiguity in the word ‘justice’ as well, as it can represent the content of the outcome of a process (referred to as ‘substantive’ justice²⁴), or the characteristics of the process itself (procedural justice). The formal concept of justice is closely related to that of “due process”. The quality of the end result is not measured by means of a normative value, but by the quality of the process involved. This could equally apply to ADR processes.²⁵ In the historical development of court systems, this quality has become equated with formality and procedure. The way information is exchanged and the use to which it can be put are an important part of that formality. The second major pier of “justice” is that the third party adjudicator or assistant who is involved, is impartial and neutral. This criterion applies equally to court- and alternative procedures.

Court processes have coercive and final characteristics. At the end of the process there is simply no further argument possible, and the “loser” is coerced into accepting whatever the outcome is. The end result produces a ‘winner’, who is “right” and a loser, who is “wrong”. This end result has replaced the primitive means of conflict determination, which could well involve physical damage to, or

²⁴ Which, somewhat boldly, may be equated with “equity” (Butler, 2003).

²⁵ Different ADR processes may have different procedural characteristics, but that does not prevent the setting of standards that can be evaluated, (NADRAC, 2004).

elimination of, the opponent. Especially in conflicts between individuals, the emotional importance of the connection between “winning” and “being right” and “loosing” and “being wrong” is very strong, and no doubt related to the more primitive instincts that produce these emotions. This may be aggravated by the availability of outcomes that contain a punitive element. In those cases, the parties are also subjected to a form of moral evaluation between them, or even against societal norms. This adds to the emotional mix that results from winning or losing a court procedure.

It would follow that the satisfaction with the outcome of a court procedure is related to degree in which the winner is found to be “right”. This may be exemplified by research that found a correlation between Plaintiffs’ positive sentiments about justice and the quantitative value of the (winning) outcome (Delaney *et al.*, 1997). Overall, however, that research showed a very poor satisfaction with court procedure as a means of resolving conflict.

In summary, increasing formality correlates with a perception of increased quality of justice. Formality relates to the procedures used, including those which regulate information exchange and the way information may be used. Alternative dispute resolution processes relax formality in order to achieve other, and more satisfactory, outcomes than the “win versus loose” approach of formal proceedings, but do so with an apparently reduced “quality of procedural justice”.

If thinking about conflict resolution takes place in terms of “winning and losing” or even “punishment”, the consensual, and more ‘mediative’ processes will always be seen to be operating under a sub-standard concept of justice, simply because they are not aimed at producing such adversarial outcomes.

This paper argues that the apparent tension between “substantive” and “procedural” justice can be relaxed by introducing im-

proved and standardised means of information exchange that can be applied in both ‘formal’ and ‘alternative’ dispute resolution procedures.

D. THE STRUCTURE OF DISPUTE RESOLUTION

The preceding sections have discussed the way in which information plays a role in the origin and development of conflict, and how regulating and formalising information exchange in dispute resolution processes is related to the concept of justice.

Highly structured and formal processes provide an environment which is more suitable for the introduction of information systems than that resulting from less formalised procedures. This is the result of the fact that formal procedures are easier to understand and describe, as they contain less variables and alternative ways to achieve an outcome. Essentially, this is why they are called “formal” in the first place.

This creates an interesting problem in the search for ways to use information technology in dispute resolution. On the one hand is the realisation that formality and rigid structures and processes are impediments on efficiency of the dispute resolution process itself, while on the other hand formalised structures and procedures are helpful to make the use of information technology in dispute resolution viable. Increasing flexibility in procedure can make the process more efficient, but more difficult to automate. A CADR system would have to provide the structure and rigidity which is required to satisfy the requirements of a “just” (and therefore formal) process and at the same time allow for the flexibility required to support consensual resolution methods that may use any of an unlimited number of alternative ways to use information. This appears to be a contradiction that cannot be resolved.

As often, the solution lies in standardisation.

It is not until standards are developed that products or services can be produced with a level of efficiency that allows large scale application. As this paper argues that information exchange is the commonality between all types of dispute resolution, it proposes that standardisation of the information exchange in the different processes can eventually lead to large scale acceptance of ADR, and to successful integration of ADR into formal adjudication processes. At the same time, the quality of information exchange in the ADR procedures can be brought up to the standard of the formal (court) processes, whereby the perception that ADR produces a lower quality of “justice” may be changed.

In order to develop the required standards of information exchange, it is necessary to understand the structure of dispute resolution processes. As was discussed above, this seems achievable for the formal methods, such as litigation and arbitration, but apparently impossible for the less formal ADR procedures.

E. THE STRUCTURE IN CONFLICT ITSELF

An explanation that is often provided for the apparent lack of structure in ADR processes is the infinite variety in human relations and endeavours. This is said to make it impossible to prescribe with any form of accuracy how an ADR procedure might be structured. To a certain extent, this could be seen to be something of a protectionist sentiment, not uncommon for new fields of expertise. The developing profession²⁶ enjoys its status as conflict resolution magician, performing rites of esoteric knowledge behind the closed doors of confidentiality, yet fails to make an impact on the international stage of major conflict situations (Mayer, 2004).

²⁶ For an interesting discussion of the meaning of “profession” in that context see (Fraser, 2001)

Every developing profession has such seemingly protectionist traits, although the mechanisms vary. To make a comparison that is relevant to the subject of this paper, information technology professionals used terminology (nowadays called geek-speak) to protect their exclusivity. And although the technology in that field is very structured, the various players excelled in each developing their own version of it. It was when one (IBM) decided to open up its technological architecture that developments really started, leading to the creation of standards (and notably the resulting dominance of Microsoft).

In the case of ADR however, the absence of uniformity and accepted standards results in a theoretical and academic foundation that cannot be relied upon for an understanding of the structure of ADR processes.²⁷

But, as is often the case, changing the perspective of the question, provides a suggestion. By changing the question from ‘understanding the structure of ADR processes’ to ‘understanding the structure of conflict’, a vast resource of material opens up, with the added bonus that much of that material is founded on a more academically solid, scientific background. This is the study of, and research in, conflict theory.

People, by the simple reason of being human, have an inbuilt and quite advanced, understanding of conflict, albeit that this understanding is mostly developed from the perspective of being a participant in conflict, or an observer of someone else’s conflict. The role of conflict in society has been pointed out before, and may explain the thorough, but mainly “instinctive” knowledge people have about conflict. This “instinctive” character also explains the tendency to shift the emphasis in a conflict to damaging or eliminating the oppo-

ment rather than the conflict (Deutsch, 1969; Fisher, 2004).²⁸ A proper theoretical understanding requires a scientific, and therefore more distant and objective, approach. As conflict is a central trait in human behaviour, there has been much study of exactly what conflict is, and how it operates. For the purpose of this project, there is one area of research particularly interesting; the formulation and research of conflict models. This type of structural approach to the mechanics of conflict fits well with the desire to describe and evaluate automated means to support conflict resolution.

F. USING CONFLICT THEORY, NOT ADR THEORY

As a result, this research into the possibility of development of an information system for dispute resolution support should be based on research into the structure of conflict itself. This proposition includes the possibility that such research and its results will be more reliable and efficient than basing it on research into the structure of ADR processes.

In line with the observations made earlier about the place of the study of ADR within the sciences, something can be said about the disciplines relevant to this project: sociology, psychology, law, information technology, and ADR itself.

The influence of sociology and psychology comes from the study of communication and information exchange in general, and conflict behaviour specifically. This may be characterised as a social psychological perspective.

²⁷ Although substantial effort is being made to develop a more sound academic basis for ADR. A good example in the Australian context is the work of NADRAC. (NADRAC, 2004)

²⁸ Or, in popular vernacular, “playing the man and not the ball”. This topic is considered in more detail under the heading “the power component” in chapter IV.

The influence of law is found in the concepts of legal procedure and justice. Additionally, as has been pointed out, all dispute resolution occurs “in the shadow of the law”.²⁹

Information technology provides tools for analysis and description of the models used, and will eventually provide the environment in which the system will operate.

The project also necessarily has a substantial statistical content, albeit not in this first phase. The analytical tools to be used to weigh and grade dispute components will be based on statistics. The ‘map’ of emotional bindings that represents the emotional characteristics of conflict communication, and the influence and use of power, will also require statistic analysis. It is further envisaged that the eventual user interface will contain graphical presentation of data, which will have to be generated using statistical tools.

²⁹ (Boulle *et al.*, 1998)

III CONFLICT STRUCTURE

A. THE USE OF MODELS

1 The purpose of models and theory

The purpose of theories or models is four-fold; they assist in description, abstraction, explanation and prediction. In this context it is necessary to consider two purposes of the use of models and theory, and to describe in what way information systems can be seen as models.

One result of the use of theory is that a language is produced, defining key concepts, which allows researchers in the field to communicate precise and concise. Another result is that common assumptions are developed, which, after testing, can be accepted as being 'fundamental' to that theory. It will be seen that terminology will have to be developed to describe functions of a CADR system, and its conceptual basis.

Models are useful in describing the parameters of information systems. In fact, an information system can be seen as a model itself, as it encloses a description of relevant entities, and the relations between them in terms of data and operations on data. For the purpose of this project information system functionality can be categorised by describing four types of modelling techniques.

(a) Models used for the simulation of reality

If a comprehensive model of an area of study can be constructed, it is theoretically possible to make an information system that accurately represents that model. If such an information system can be populated with a sufficient quantity of relevant data, a representation of reality is the result, which can be used to experiment and in-

investigate. This activity is generally referred to as computer simulation. The advantage of this approach is that the reality may be impossible to investigate because of physical or economic considerations. Simulation models can be used to represent situations, which are in the past or future, or to demonstrate the result of alternative actions (The so-called what-if simulations).

A large number of this type of models have been developed that are used in dispute resolution, not because they model the dispute environment itself, but because they model the subject matter of specific disputes, and allow the parties to study the effects of various alternative proposals. Practical examples that have been found are environmental models of river systems, models for wildlife preservation projects, coastal projects, highway construction, traffic systems, wastewater treatment plants, agricultural development etc. The function of these models can be seen as the introduction of objective criteria (Fisher, Ury, & Patton, 1991). Their functionality helps to provide a good understanding of the trade-offs that are made in negotiation or dispute resolution. This function may be compared with that of the white-board in mediation; it helps in visualising alternative outcomes. Especially in complicated disputes with many inter-related issues, computer models are inherently more powerful and flexible than their white-board counterparts.

Another function that such models provide is that they enable disputants to argue about the algorithms that are used in their construction. Agreement on the way representative models operate provides a 'rule system' which can replace emotional and fundamental differences. Rule systems are an accepted means of resolving conflict between parties with fundamentally different objectives. Models that describe an abstraction of reality can provide the objective

information on which the agreed rule system can operate, resulting in what can be best described as “derivative” compromise.³⁰

(b) Models used in primary processes

Information systems in primary processes replace direct intervention by human agents. Examples are industrial process control and on-line trading systems. Such systems contain a (data) subset of a real situation, and operate on the data in that subset. This type of systems are models in the sense that they use a representation of reality to work on, but this is always a representation that has first been accepted as an abstract form of reality itself. Examples of such accepted abstractions are process status parameters, bank transactions, email messages, and on-line theatre bookings. In the current context, any functionality that would signal deficiencies in logic, or that notifies information exchange opportunities, would be in this category.

The litigation support systems that are described in the appendix have functions that are in this category, and it can be expected that further development of those systems may eventually replace most of the paperwork that is involved in the presentation of evidence in adjudication processes. This also applies to the information exchange in other dispute resolution processes. Ideally, the information contained in a CADR system, where relevant, must be organised in such a way that transfer to, or integration into, such litigation support systems is possible. Whenever information contained in electronic form transcends the boundary between information and evidence, consideration must be given to its admissibility and the way it is presented (Harvey, 2003).

³⁰ Agreement between fundamentally opposed parties is not possible. Agreement on the rules to be used to resolve conflict or find compromise may be possible. Application of those rules on accepted objective information then leads to a result which is accepted by implication, or ‘derived’ from the agreed rules.

(c) Models used in secondary processes

Information systems that are used to support secondary processes, such as accounting systems, can also be seen as a model representing reality, albeit that they operate at a higher level of abstraction. This is the result of the fact that those systems represent what can be described as a model itself. In the example mentioned, an accounting system, the accounting process itself is a simplified representation of business activities, expressed in monetary values only (a representation itself). In the context of the CADR system, it will be obvious that most of its functionality will be in this category.

Abstractions will be used to describe conflict situations, and these will be used to construct a model. An example is the development of conflict description languages, such as Conflict Resolution Modelling Language CRML (Hendler, 2004), which has the potential to support algorithms that may be used for logical processing. Game theory and semantic analysis can be integrated to develop a sort of conflict resolution mathematics. (Lodder & Zeleznikow, 2005).

It appears that the development of this type of logic is based on “conflict resolution” in technical environments, such as in data-networks, missile guidance systems, airline traffic control systems etc. In a further development, the use is extended into planning work within specialised organisations, such as engineering or construction projects, and a next step is in more general conflict resolution environments. It is interesting to note that there is development of computer models for these specific technical or organisational settings, and also for international conflict situations (a field of study called peace science (Isard, 1992)), but that no concrete applications have been found for the area of general civil dispute. A number of projects are underway were it is attempted for specific types of dis-

putes or relatively narrow sections of resolution techniques (Conley Tyler *et al.*, 2003).

Application on the wider scale of civil conflict requires the ‘translation’ of actual conflict information into abstractions that allow processing by means of logical algorithms. This translation may be achieved by involving the use of semantic modelling.

(d) Semantic modelling

Semantic modelling represents a technique from the artificial intelligence field.³¹ The concept behind it is that by structuring semantics in such a way that ambiguity is avoided, a use of language results that can be interpreted by an automaton (e.g. a computer). In practice this means reducing the meaning of words to singular, well defined, expressions,³² and the construction of grammar suitable for logical processing. The ‘traditional’ information system analysis as described above, can be recognised in this approach, as it also requires definition of data (the meaning of words), and processes (the structure of grammar). The concept is however, at a higher level of abstraction, and is therefore more flexible to theoretical application, and definition of standards. A problem with semantic modelling is that it requires capabilities to interpret and work with data and processes that have not been contemplated at the time of describing the information system. It therefore requires the definition of meta-data,

³¹ And artificial intelligence itself has been described by Lodder & Zeleznikow as: “Artificial intelligence (AI) is commonly associated with anthropomorphic computers performing amazing feats, as in movies like *The Matrix* and *Minority Report*, AI is actually a much broader field of study whose results are not always mind-blowing. So what is AI? Two humorous definitions are “whatever computers can’t do yet and “trying to solve by computer any problem that a human can solve faster.” Basically, AI involves the study of automated human intelligence. This includes both practically-oriented research, such as building computer applications that perform tasks requiring human intelligence, and fundamental research, such as determining how to represent knowledge in a computer-comprehensible form. At the intersection of AI on the one hand and law on the other lies a field dedicated to the use of advanced computer technology for legal purposes: AI & Law. “ (Lodder *et al.*, 2005)

which are data structures that describe the purpose of data and processes in such a way that the automaton processing the data can determine the type of data or processes to apply in a given situation. This concept can be applied to very large, and publicly accessible computer systems and/or networks, such as the World Wide Web, leading to a concept called “the semantic web” (Berners-Lee, 1998; Berners-Lee *et al.*, 2001).

The concept can be best explained by the following diagram, which shows the basis layer of web-data, standardised both in form and locator references, with the emerging layers of RDF/XML that will eventually support the ontology and logical layers that will provide the distributed application software concept which is part of the semantic web concept.

Figure 2 The Semantic Web (Hendler, 2001)

Applied at a smaller scale, that concept would provide a radically different approach to implementing a CADR system. Rather than implementing a system that requires re-entry and re-structuring of data, it could be based directly on existing documents and com-

³² An often used term in that field is “ontology”, defined as “the definition of a concept.”

munications between the parties, and it would use logic to determine and potentially provides clues to resolve the issues in conflict.

It must be appreciated that this type of semantic analysis is still very remote from the discourse analysis (Potter & Wetherell, 1987; Tuffin, 2005) that would be required to extract relevant motives and emotions from what is expressed, but it is a certain step in that direction. At the end of chapter V some practical examples are provided to demonstrate in which direction semantic modelling can be developed.

2 *The use of statistical methods*

The development of conflict between contesting parties includes elements of chance and probability (Chatterji, 1992). Statistics is the science of probability, and as such has an important role to play in the analysis of and predictions for conflict development. The crux for the use of statistical methods lies in the development of models and the quality of the associated data on which statistical operations can be performed. Deficient models or inaccurate data invariably lead to the “garbage in – garbage out” axiom that is well-known in the fields of information technology and artificial intelligence.

The logic supporting the use of statistical methods and models relies on the concept that events can be described within a range of possible variations, whereby each variation can be indicated to be within a range of probability of occurring, depending on given variables. If such a model can be constructed, statistical methods can be used to calculate probabilities of more complex combinations of events, or to determine the interaction between the various variables. A good example is game theory, where decision situations are reduced to simple choices between discrete alternatives. As a result, a limited number of outcomes are possible, which can be rated accord-

ing to desirability for each party. Based on that rating, a party's likely strategy can be predicted. Statisticians apply similar techniques to more complex situations, such as in conflicts between nations, and replace distinct choices with probable choices, depending on expected outcomes. The resulting field of study ("peace science") predicts tactics and strategies, and their outcomes within ranges of probability.

Statistics can also be used to compare individual value systems, when a neutral standard is available. As an example, if a reliable means to measure conflict behaviour is available, and each party can be rated against such a standard, predictions can be made for the resulting conflict dynamics. Additionally, measuring overall conflict behaviour of a party can produce a standard that can be used to rate emotions towards individual issues, in order to create 'weighted' ratings for conflict behaviour on individual issues. Comparison of conflict behaviour ratings then becomes possible between the parties without distortion by overall conflict attitudes.

As an example, a party that has an overall dominant conflict behaviour (see chapter IV) would rate higher on dominance for all individual issues as well, making comparison on an issue by issue basis impossible against the ratings of a party that has an overall accommodating conflict behaviour. By first comparing the measurements on the individual ratings with the overall conflict behaviour will produce comparable rankings between the parties.

3 *Model requirements*

The models developed in this project must be suitable to support, and be supported by, a 'language of conflict', for the use of data and logic. It is appropriate to determine at this stage of the project which overall structure for the modelling approach will be used.

Given the development of the descriptive logic of semantics, and given the fact that conflict is ultimately about communication and therefore language, it appears reasonable to follow an approach that will allow use and adaptation of the recent development of the concept of the “semantic web”. Although this decision has little direct visible impact on this stage of the project, it requires that descriptions of elements of the models, and interactions between them can ultimately be ‘translated’ to statements using RDF/XML³³-compatible descriptors and syntax specification, or applications of these.

B. CONFLICT: STATICS AND DYNAMICS

1 Why create this distinction

Conflict models that integrate dynamic and static perspectives are rare. Authors in the field of conflict study seem to choose one approach or the other. A reason for that is possibly that models that capture both dynamic and static variables are inherently more complicated. Another reason will be that static and dynamic models of conflict present entirely different perspectives, which are difficult to integrate satisfactorily. A proposition of this paper is that completely separating static and dynamic presentation of conflict will never result in a reliable model, although separation helps to understand conflict relationships (static), and conflict development (dynamic).

The distinction can be maintained in order to facilitate research, and to optimise the construction of models for each representation, but ultimately a combination, and preferably an integration of these approaches must be achieved.

³³ Resource Description Framework, see www.w3.org/RDF.

2 *The relation between static and dynamic description*

The ‘traditional’ communication models act as a simplified visual means of conceptualising a communication situation and show how the various components interact (Sligo, Olsson, & Wallace, 1997). For the purpose of this paper, such a situational model is termed a “static model” of conflict, and is defined as a ‘snapshot’ view of the conflict situation. Such a “snapshot” would contain the components and relationships of the traditional communication model and their descriptors or values, plus those that are specific to conflict communication. The purpose of the “snapshot” approach is to facilitate the combination with the dynamic model at a later stage. When the static description is defined as a ‘snapshot’, it is obvious that another ‘snapshot’ can be made at another point in time. The difference between the descriptors and values for the different snapshots then becomes a measure of the dynamics of the conflict. The description of the effect of the dynamics thus established, must coincide with, or be represented in the dynamic model.

The dynamic model ought to provide a “flow chart” describing the order or alternative orders for various events to take place. In other words, it provides relationships in time. A dynamic model should therefore provide clues as to how interaction operates, what the structure of any recursivity is, and how choices and alternatives influence the course of events.

This may be compared with the approach taken in elementary physics. If one considers the movement of an object under the influence of a force, say gravity, that object, and the forces acting on it, can be described in any ‘static’ position in which it will be in for an immeasurable short period of time. It can also be described in terms of its relative position as a function of time. Connecting both approaches are the formulae describing its movement, relative to time, and the speed of the object at any point on its trajectory. For an ob-

ject dropped from a certain height at time $t=0$, its relative distance from the drop-off point is given by the formula $S_t=V_0t + \frac{1}{2}at^2$. The speed at any point is given by the formula $V_t=V_0 + at$. (where V_0 is the starting speed, a is the force of gravity, and t is the elapsed time). These formulae are related, as one is the other's differential.

The reason for providing this example is to demonstrate that static and dynamic observations of the same process are directly related, and that those relationships can be described. A very general way of phrasing that relationship would be to say that there is always a cause for each action, which is of course one of the principles underlying the scientific method. Application of these fundamentals to conflict modelling research, underpins the need to combine static and dynamic representations. The CADR system will therefore need to be based on study of both static and dynamic models, and provide the necessary relationship descriptions.

As may be concluded from the comparison with physics, it is theorised that analytical (Chatterji, 1992) and statistical (Coolican, 2004) techniques can eventually be used to describe relationships in the model, and to evaluate information.

Eventually, conflict can be seen as a constellation of changing relationships between the parties in conflict, and between the parties and the substantive issues. Conflict is characterised by action and counteraction (the theory of 'moves'). This creates the dynamics of cause and effect, whereby each party considers the change that has resulted from its own and the opponent's actions, and then decides on its next move. Conflict development can therefore be seen as a string of static situations, connected by the 'moves' that take place over time. By recording conflict information at a sufficient level of detail, and by including time related information, a narrative of developing conflict can be constructed that will eventually be helpful in analysing the impact of each individual action and the related con-

flict behaviour. A useful metaphor would be that of a multi-dimensional movie that can be viewed at any speed and from any perspective and that can be stopped to investigate details of the forces operating on the parties, and the relationships between them, at any point in time.

IV CONFLICT THEORY

This chapter provides a brief overview of the main concepts of conflict theory, including references to the relevance of these concepts for the development of a CADR system. A start is made to develop formal descriptions that will be necessary in the CADR system development.

A. CONTRASTING STATEMENTS, THE ORIGIN OF CONFLICT

A first observation is that two statements can be made about conflict, which are both obviously valid, but lead to opposing conclusions:

“Existence and development of society requires cooperation between individuals. This creates tensions, resulting in conflict. Conflict is therefore an unwanted, but unavoidable feature of social interaction.”

And:

“Conflict creates tensions that drive the development of society, and conflict is therefore a necessary feature of improvement through social interaction.”

The first statement sees conflict as a result of the human drive for development and advancement. In this view conflict has a negative connotation, conflict is to be avoided, or resolved as soon as possible. This view is represented in the ‘classic’ philosophical approach to social conflict. It can be traced back to Plato and Aristotle and was further developed in writings of the “social contract” theorists, notably Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau. Ultimately it leads to

the view that conflict is abnormal and dysfunctional, and should be eradicated.³⁴

The second statement has the opposite perspective, in that development is itself fuelled by conflict-based motivations (The ‘survival of the fittest’ theory). Support for this approach is found in the work of Charles Darwin (Darwin, 1871), and philosophers that founded work on the evolutionary theories, such as John Dewey (Dewey, 1957). This observation leads to the conclusion that conflict is not something to be avoided or eradicated, quite the contrary; the thesis is that conflict is necessary for the proper functioning of groups, together with stability and order, in other words, conflict, but well-managed and in a stable environment.³⁵

B. THE CENTRAL ASSUMPTIONS OF CONFLICT THEORY

The study of conflict recognises central assumptions, which propose that conflict behaviour requires that a party to a conflict constantly analyses the conflict and the impact of its own and the other party’s behaviour on it. Each party evaluates and describes the conflict in relation to its own goals, values and beliefs. Further behaviour and communication is aimed at influencing the situation in the direction of the own goals, which may change in the process, and which are not necessarily communicated. In other words, conflict behaviour is made up of actions, and communications, aimed at achieving more or less formally stated goals.

The actions can relate to making changes to objects in dispute or in the relationship parameters between the parties, and/or can be aimed at achieving information exchange. Hence, an action contains

³⁴ Such views were held by sociologists such as Elton Mayo and Talcott Parsons. (See Rahim, 2001).

³⁵ See Rahim, 2001, for a brief expose on the work of sociologists as Mills, Dahrendorf, Bernard and Coser who hold this ‘functional’ view of conflict. Eisaguirre, (Eisaguirre, 2002) goes one step further and embraces conflict as a positive driving force, to be used purposively to achieve organisational goals.

a communication component. Therefore actions aimed at change, will lead to observation of (the consequences of) the action itself and its (perceived) information exchange component. As can be seen, the words ‘action’ and communication’ are imprecise, and will have to be defined without ambiguity to be useful.

Communication in conflict situations is structured to convey information aimed at three objectives:

- To exchange information on substantive issues in dispute.
- To exchange information about the relationship issues between the parties, with the aim to influence that relationship. This involves the use of power or influence, to change relationship parameters.
- To exchange information attempting to affect the communication environment itself e.g. procedure, topics, place etc, in order to achieve tactical advantages.

Essentially, conflict is a form of communication, and therefore, interactive behaviour. The main differences with ‘ordinary’ communication are the emotional aspect and the move/countermove character of conflict communication. When the emphasis shifts from communication about substantive issues to communication about relationship issues and formalities the importance of the emotional content increases. Communication with third parties aimed at influencing the opponent or the issues will also occur, and often leads to the introduction of additional issues, and further relationship complications. This has been described thus:³⁶

“Typically a competitive process tends to produce the following effects: communication between conflicting parties is unreliable and impoverished. The available communication channels and opportunities are not utilised or they are used in an attempt to mislead or intimidate the other. Little confidence is placed in information that is obtained directly from the other,

³⁶ (Deutsch, 1969) at pg 12, as quoted by (Moore, 2003), at pg 169

espionage and other circuitous means of obtaining information are relied upon. The poor communication enhances the possibility of error and misinformation of the sort which is likely to reinforce the pre-existing orientations and expectations toward the other.”

The recursive character of conflict communication results in a series of moves and countermoves. Communication takes place in steps, each step is made partly in response to the step taken by the opponent, and partly in pursuit of the own objectives.

When the subject of communication is a disagreement about a substantive matter, which cannot be resolved, the information exchange will increasingly emphasise on the secondary and tertiary communication objectives. This will not assist in actually resolving the dispute, and more, and probably ‘stronger’, communication is deemed necessary. These factors form the background of conflict’s recursive character, and its ‘vortex’ effect. In other words, conflict development has a spiralling rather than a circular morphology.

This paper proposes that communication aimed at the secondary and tertiary objectives involves the implied or threatened use of ‘power’ in the relationship between the parties, and is the source of developing emotions in a conflict situation. The emotions drive the escalation of conflict.

In order to be able to assist parties in communicating about the substantive matters that must be resolved, the emotional (power) parameters of the information exchange must be reduced or removed, or at least separated from the information exchange about substantive matters. Emotional issues sustain conflict behaviour, and all communication tends to become emotionally charged. If conflict-supporting behaviour can be suppressed or understood for what it is, the chance of finding solutions increases.

In order to be able to develop tools for separation of the emotional or conflict related information from that about the substantive issues, conflict behaviour must be understood and described with sufficient, logical, accuracy. This is the main concept behind this project.

C. A DEFINITION OF CONFLICT

There are many definitions of conflict, tailored to the purposes of their creators. The word “conflict” itself has no rigid definition; the word may describe a situation or behaviour. It has static and dynamic connotations. The word is also indeterminable vague as to the seriousness of the event. It may describe a simple quarrel or a war between nations. For the purpose of this project a definition will be used which is based on a definition by Wilmot (Wilmot, 1998):

“Conflict is an expressed struggle between two parties with perceived interdependent goals.”

The operative words in this definition are ‘expressed’, ‘struggle’, ‘perceived’, and ‘interdependent’. These main elements are found in most conflict definitions, often accompanied by further elements describing specific types of conflict, such as zero-sum conflicts, positive sum conflicts, or mixed-purpose conflicts. This distinction indicates one of the ways conflict can be classified, by a typology of the outcome. Other classifications of conflict are based on the source of the conflict, on a typology of the parties to it, or the environment in which it takes place. This paper will not deal with the theoretical classification of conflict in any detail, but some attention is now given to the core elements of the definition above.

1 Expression, the threshold theory.

A conflict is not recognised as such until it has been expressed. This recognises two distinct characteristics. The first is the simple

expression that the parties consider that a conflict exists. The second relates to what Baron (Baron, 1990) refers to as a “threshold level of intensity”. Although both may appear trivial, this is an area where a CADR system may prove helpful. Many disputes go unexpressed for considerable time. The result can be that by the time the dispute is eventually expressed, it has matured to such a state that simple resolution is no longer possible. An effective and assessable CADR system may provide the infrastructure for earlier attempts to express a dispute situation, with a consequently higher chance of resolution. It is suggested that many disputes end up in Court simply because there was no communication mechanism available between the parties to break the ‘unavoidable spiral’ of an escalating conflict. There is statistical evidence that many disputes are settled “on the steps of the court house”, for instance in the USA in 2003 42% of cases filed were settled, and only 8% of cases that were started was concluded to a hearing.³⁷ This would support the view that it is only during the preparation of litigation that the parties become aware of all relevant information, especially with regards to the exact position of the opponent. This evidence also demonstrates that, as was to be expected, judicial settlements conferences and negotiations between counsel, have a substantial success rate (District Court Claims Subcommittee, 2005; Saville-Smith, 2004).

These observations have relevance for the development of a CADR system, by concluding that such a system must provide an environment in which parties can exchange information in the early stages of conflict, or even before it is expressed as such. Conceptually, one could imagine an environment (e.g. a website), to which both parties could upload all relevant documents, including email, links to websites, photographs, video, etc. That would provide a common repository of what would eventually become documentary

³⁷ www.ncsconline.org/D_Research/csp/CSP_Main_Page.html.

evidence. Such material can be structured in the way described below, and the parties could be assisted in each describing the conflict. Such a description could be guided into the semantic structure as proposed, and include links to the documents. By applying semantic analysis, it may be possible to ‘filter’ emotional content from the messages, and create an “objective” narrative in which the parties could identify where the substantive disagreements are located. If that can be achieved, before the parties make and enforce the emotional bindings that prevent information exchange altogether, resolution is more likely to succeed.

2 *Struggle, the power component*

The use of the word struggle indicates that coercion (power) is used in achieving objectives, which are not only aimed at the substantive issues in dispute, but also at the other party or the relationship between the parties. Another definition of conflict (Coser, 1956) expresses that more specifically:

“Conflict is a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power, and resources, a struggle in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralise, injure, or eliminate rivals.”

Although this definition includes what can be described as an extreme position, it cannot be denied (as was discussed previously) that in a developing conflict the emphasis tends to shift quite rapidly from resolving issues to damaging the opponent. These sentiments are exactly what drives conflict, and frustrate resolution. To a certain extent, such sentiments appear to be based on a primeval mechanism that uses conflict as a way of determining which individual should have access to a scarce resource, to the exclusion of another individual.

3 Perceptions, not facts determine conflict behaviour.

The word 'perception' is relevant in combination with the word 'interdependent'. Parties to any form of cooperation have individual goals in mind, which may be interdependent, or non-congruent. Therefore negotiation has to take place about how the optimal goal satisfaction is to be achieved. As discussed previously, conflict is normally the result of that negotiation process ending up in an unbalanced situation. It is important to recognise that goal incongruity is mostly of a 'perceived' nature, as a result of parties formulating their goals in terms of desired outcomes rather than in terms of needs they seek to fulfil.³⁸

The most important connotation of 'perception' in a conflict situation however, is the escalating force that results from perceived motives behind the other party's actions. As communication breaks down, parties use unrelated, and often unreliable, information to draw conclusions about the reasons and background of the other party's actions. Perception extends not only to what is actually observed, but also to the underlying motives. As a result, each party creates a mental image of the characteristics, objectives and intentions of the other party, and uses this image to explain and 'understand' the other's actions. Such attributions have a remarkable strong and lasting influence (Folger, Poole, & Stutman, 2005).

The perceived intentions will tend to 'overflow' from substantive to relationship objectives. In other words, and as an example, a party can possibly perceive a substantive goal statement by the other as aimed at an underlying, but undisclosed, relationship objective. The statement "I want you to fix that sink, and I want it done tomorrow", may well be aimed more at a power and relationship objective (I am the boss), than at the urgent need for the sink to be repaired.

³⁸ Or in positions, rather than in interests. (Fisher *et al.*, 1991)

The party thus spoken to will interpret the statement very differently, based on existing relationship and emotional parameters.

It is conceptualised that information exchange about perceived objectives and their components will eventually be a helpful instrument in assisting parties to resolve emotional issues, where these frustrate a resolution of substantive issues. The problem is that parties in conflict have many psychological obstacles to discuss and resolve emotional issues. They will deny that emotional or irrational considerations colour their opinions, and they will not admit that emotions based on perceived objectives of the other party have played a role. The closer the issues are interwoven, the more difficult it is to talk about the reasons behind positions and statements.

The advantage of separating the emotional matters at the level of individual objectives is that communication of emotional matters can be restricted to only those issues where it is strictly necessary, and only to the extent necessary to resolve the substantive issue.

The important, and frustrating, role of incorrect perceptions can be brought to light gradually and with minimum “loss of face”, leading to a re-evaluation of the conflict situation. This will assist in changing conflict behaviour towards a more integrative style.

4 Interdependent goals

The word interdependent expresses that the parties’ goals or objectives have a relationship, whereby optimal goal satisfaction for both parties from the available resources is perceived to be impossible. “Resources” must be seen in its broadest meaning and may include emotional or relationship resources or social or even psychological resources such as social status, self-perception, acknowledgment etc. Essential in the understanding of ‘interdependent’ is the notion that the actions of one party have an impact on the way the other party is able to achieve its goals. Again, parties often operate

without much objective and reliable information about the other party's goals. Any information exchange to improve that situation is likely to reduce conflict escalation.

D. THE FUNCTION OF CONFLICT

Conflict generally arises in situations where previously some cooperation or relationship was present. Conflict can be better understood from that pre-condition.

Where cooperation can take shape in a number of alternative configurations, these will have different results in terms of distribution of efforts and benefits. Economic theory requires that each individual or group will seek to achieve the cooperation alternative that provides for maximisation of the own benefits, while minimising the own efforts. As a result, the choice of the cooperation alternative to be used is subject to a 'negotiation' process.

At the conclusion of negotiation the parties will have obtained a substantive and relationship configuration which reflects the cooperation parameters between them. In theory, the outcome is balanced and rational.

When one party uses any form of power or coercion to achieve an unbalanced outcome, the other party will accrue a level of frustration. This is the point where emotional "links" are created with the substantive and relationship components of the negotiated cooperation. When the balance between the relative strength of these emotions and the perceived value of the cooperation effort is disturbed, conflict arises. Consequently, the presence of conflict requires, by definition, a compounded situation where disagreement about substantive issues is complicated with relationship and emotional issues.

At some point in the development and escalation of conflict, its "costs" will outweigh the benefits of the underlying cooperation.

Perfectly rational disputants would terminate the conflict when that point is reached. Often however, the emotional “links” prevent the parties from acting rational. This explains why a conflicting relationship is often continued well past the point where economic rationale would require a termination of the cooperation altogether. Parties feel compelled to continue a dispute, against better judgement. This results in large costs, not only in economic, but also in emotional and societal terms. The conclusion is therefore that the utilitarian function of conflict is eroded when disputing parties become involved in emotional and relationship issues to the extent that the rational point of termination is transgressed. The resulting perception of conflict is a negative one.

While on the one hand conflict has merit, too much conflict is counterproductive. It can be said that conflict has functional and dysfunctional outcomes,³⁹ of which examples can be given, as well as some characteristics. (Coser, 1956; Deutsch, 1969; Folger *et al.*, 2005; Kriesberg, 1998; Lulofs, 1994; Rahim, 2001).

1 Functional (productive) conflict

Functional conflict tends to focus on substantive issues; once these are resolved the relationship issues are often resolved as well, there is a balance between competitiveness and cooperation. Parties use a variety of behaviours to come to acceptable solutions, and operate from a belief that win/win outcomes are possible. In order to achieve this, goals are defined broadly, on the basis of interests.

Productive outcomes include:

- Conflict may stimulate innovation, creativity, and growth.
- Societal decision making may be improved, both in process and in development of precedent.

³⁹ Folger et al (2005) use the words ‘productive’ and ‘destructive’ outcomes, to make a similar analysis to Rahim’s.

- Alternative solutions to problems may be found.
- Conflict may lead to synergetic solutions to common problems.
- Individual and group performance may be enhanced.
- Individuals and groups may be forced to search for new approaches.
- Individuals and groups may be forced to articulate their positions.
- Conflict helps people to find the boundaries of their relationship with others.
- Conflict facilitates the reconciliation of legitimate interests.
- Conflict resolution may lead to a desirable re-distribution of resources or social power.
- Conflict may be the basis for positive personal change, and helps build empathy at a personal level.

2 *Dysfunctional (destructive) conflict*

Dysfunctional conflict is based on aggression and attempts to hurt the other party. Undercutting the other party's interests is used as a means of improving position. Force and coercion are used to 'win' rather than resolve a conflict. Behaviours are rigid and inflexible; goals are defined narrowly, and in terms of positions and ultimatums. Parties withdraw from communication and involve advocates; procedure and communication is formalised and censored.

Destructive outcomes include:

- Conflict may cause stress, burnout and dissatisfaction.
- Communication between individuals and groups may be reduced.
- A climate of distrust and suspicion develops.
- Relationships are damaged.
- Performance may be reduced.
- Conflict interferes with development and innovation.

- Costs are made to sustain conflict and ‘win’, rather than resolve issues.

3 *The role of resolution and adjudication systems*

The evaluation of the quality of conflict outcomes will differ depending on the position of the observer. While a conflict may be dysfunctional for the participants, it can be productive for society as a whole, as a result of re-distribution of resources, reinforcement of procedural justice, or re-assessment of perceived values.

A successful society will therefore seek to create systems to manage conflict and its excesses, in order to have the benefit of the functional outcomes, while reducing the costs of the dysfunctional outcomes. The more diverse a society is, and the more complex its organisation, the more chance there is that conflict will develop. This recognises that in a plural society disagreement and conflict is inevitable, and can develop between parties with fundamentally different beliefs and morals. Conflict resolution processes and their related rules are a way to manage conflict in plural societies. In other words, fundamental disagreement on substantive issues is accepted as long as there is agreement on the way the resulting conflicts are dealt with and decided. The emphasis shifts from the issues themselves to the efficiency and fairness of the resolution processes.

Some conflicts and their results cross the boundaries of what is considered morally acceptable for the society as a whole. For these situations a separate body of control mechanisms is created, e.g. criminal law, which is outside the scope of this work. Additionally, a society requires systems to change its decision making rules, which may also result in conflict. These types of conflict are not considered either. The focus of this paper is on conflicts between individuals, operating within the rule systems of the society of which they are a member, and who seek the more or less formal mechanisms that are available to them to resolve or determine their differences.

Initially such decision making powers were placed with the leaders or rulers of societies, and later such functions were provided for by means of courts of law, following from the idea that it is a function of the administrators (i.e. government) to provide conflict management systems. These systems however, are expensive, difficult to operate, and not necessarily efficient. As a result, developments to create alternatives, more suitable to the needs of modern society are taking place. This includes the developing field of alternative dispute resolution. In addition, conflict ‘management’ (and ADR) seek to intervene in conflict situations at an earlier point than that of judicial determination. It is thought that maintaining or restoring productive interaction patterns is the basis for resolving, rather than deciding, conflict (Folger *et al.*, 2005).

E. THE ROLE OF POWER IN CONFLICT

The many definitions of power have in common that power originates from, and exists only in the context of a relationship, and is not an attribute of an individual in a general sense.

Power can be described as the ability of one party to influence directly or indirectly,⁴⁰ the behaviour or emotions of the other party, the capability of the other party to achieve its goals, or its freedom to maintain its attitudes, beliefs and values.

Differences in relative power are a logical and accepted result of the organisation of society, and are part of the context of any transaction or negotiation situation. Typically, both parties have a certain power over each other, the extent of which is governed by the scope and type of their relationship. It is when a form of power is used to achieve objectives against the other party’s interests, or out-

⁴⁰ Additionally the terms “virtual” power (using power by displaying potential use), or “hidden power” (power to exclude issues, which therefore never emerge), are found (Folger *et al.*, 2005).

side of the negotiated or established arrangement that conflict arises (Blau, 1964).

Another way to analyse this (Kriesberg, 1998), is that conflict arises at the point where one party comes to the conclusion that not the objects in dispute must be changed to achieve its goals, but some characteristic of the other party. This can only be achieved by coercion, reward or force. As the first two have obviously failed (they are within the sphere of substantive objects), only force (power) remains as a tool to achieve the desired result.

The use of power to achieve goals does not necessarily arise from a negative context, it may well be that a cooperation is structured in such a way that power differences are necessarily the primary basis for decision making, because the type of cooperation requires this (e.g. army, fire brigade), or that consensual decision making is not worth the effort (Kotter, 1985).

Emotional issues come in existence when a party perceives that the other party is using power characteristics of the relationship for ulterior (win versus loose) purposes (Fisher, 2004). The resulting emotions provide the motivation for (escalating) conflict behaviour, aimed at restoring what is perceived as a balance. That balance can be found by adjusting substantive, relationship, or social parameters.

As a conflict goes through its moves and countermoves in an escalating spiral, the parties use the various resources they have to exert power over the other party. Obviously, if one party is in a position to exercise substantially more power than the other, a situation arises where the less powerful party may have to accept whatever the powerful party is seeking to achieve. Because power can be based on many different aspects of a relationship (directly and indirectly) it is not often that one party has so much power that it can simply ignore the other completely, and pursue its objectives independently. It is therefore important to consider the various power dimensions as

they relate to each of the issues in conflict. It is not exceptional that parties have substantial misunderstandings about the other's perception or intended use of power in relation to specific issues. Lack of information on this aspect is typically substituted by assumptions based on perceptions and opinions.

Use of power is often overt or by implication, and only very rarely the subject of explicit information exchange or negotiation. Additionally, since power is based on aspects of a relationship and parties change their relationship in the course of a conflict, the sources and use of power change.

Typically, when the dispute resolution environment increases in formality, the sources of power become restricted to generally accepted and "common" power sources such as legal entitlements, economic power etc. In such environments, an objective determination of relative power becomes relevant, and the skill with which formalised power is exercised attains more importance. The role and use of procedure becomes an important aspect in the conflict process.

The way power differences are used has a strong social and cultural context. The influence of 'peer' groups and value and belief systems (culture) play a role. Large differences between parties in this respect can result in continuation of conflict without the parties understanding why the other party does not terminate the conflict situation. Conflict is then continued "by default" as an institutionalised pattern of behaviour.

F. CONFLICT BEHAVIOUR

Conflict behaviour has been the subject of study aimed at finding determinants of behaviour in interpersonal conflict. This started with simple models capturing cooperative versus competitive behaviour (typically in zero-sum conflict situations), or conflict engage-

ment versus conflict avoidance behaviour. Over time more characteristics were added and two-dimensional models developed, notably those by Blake & Mouton, Pruitt & Rubin, and Rahim. (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Pruitt, 1983; Pruitt & Rubin, 1986; Rahim, 1983, 2001).

Rahim (2001) developed questionnaires based on the more complicated 2-dimensional and 5-factor models, which were extensively tested for statistical consistency.⁴¹ Although these are mainly aimed at conflict management within organisations, they would provide a reliable basis for the determination of more general conflict behaviour. The related conflict behaviour model can be represented in the following diagram:

Figure 3 Conflict behaviour diagram

Apart from the dimensions of concern for self and concern for others, the “integrative” and “distributive” dimensions as used by other authors (Lewicki, Saunders, & Minton, 2001) are included in this model as the diagonals from the integrative to avoiding style (the

⁴¹ These questionnaires are called the “Rahim Organisational Inventory I and II instruments” and have been used in hundreds of studies and consequent papers and articles. See <http://members.aol.com/mgt2000/roci-bib.htm/> for a list of these.

integrative dimension, from ‘high’ to ‘low’), and from the dominating to the obliging style (the distributive dimension from ‘low’ to ‘high’. For the purpose of the CADR system this analysis tool can be used to determine conflict behaviour in general, and at the level of individual issues. A number of questionnaire type instruments have been identified,⁴² on the basis of which this tool can be implemented.

Determination of conflict behaviour at the level of an individual objective (Q) will provide a value for the “intention” (n) component of the emotional component related to that objective.⁴³

The two-dimensional model captures conflict behaviour between parties at a general or objective level, but is primarily aimed at negotiation type behaviour where “resources” are at issue.

Additionally there is conflict behaviour which is not aimed at the other party, but may be aimed at the environment at large, at other agents, such as dispute participants, unrelated third parties, or aimed matters such as self-esteem. “Face work” is an example of that type of conflict behaviour, which is mainly used to reduce the effects of cognitive dissonance. A vast array of research and measurement instruments is available to determine the effect of cognitive dissonance on behaviour.

In conclusion, conflict behaviour results from the emotional components involved in a dispute. Conversely, the relevance and extent of these emotional components can be derived from studying or analysing conflict behaviour.

⁴² The Rahim LOCI-I (Rahim, 2001), Rahim’s questionnaire from his 1984 article, an adaptation by Ozcelic, S: “*The Relationship Between Culture and Conflict Resolution Styles: The Results of Survey Methodology*” at the Institute for Conflict Analysis and Resolution Research and Higher Education Symposium. The National Conference on Peace and Conflict Resolution (NCPCR 2001-10th Biennial Conference), The George Mason University, Fairfax, VA, June 7-10, 2001, or the Thomas Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument, presented at 153.707 Theory of conflict, Massey University, April 2004.

⁴³ This will be discussed in detail in chapter V.

G. CLIMATE

Climate is defined as the relatively enduring quality of a social unit that is experienced in common by its members, and arises from and influences their interaction and behaviour (Folger *et al.*, 2005).

This definition indicates that both behaviour and interaction are influenced by the climate of the social environment in which the conflict situation occurs. This is relevant to describe the environmental influences in the conflict models, but also in relation to the characteristics of a CADR system. For the purpose of this paper, the conflict resolution environment can eventually be assumed to be reduced to the exchange that takes place via the CADR system. The virtual environment created by the system becomes the metaphor for the “climate” of the conflict resolution. It follows that the user environment (the user interface) must be designed with the importance of climate in mind. It may be assumed that most parties using a CADR system will be one time users, and that only advisers or third parties will be using the system on a more frequent basis. Consequently, the system must be very simple to understand and use, as the least desired side effect is additional stress.

H. THE ROLE OF INFORMATION EXCHANGE IN CONFLICT

This paper is concerned with the way people operate in negotiation- and conflict situations, and especially the role information exchange plays in these situations. People rely on information to make decisions, and that information is often obtained from the negotiation or conflict opponent. In both negotiation and conflict situations there is a perceived advantage in incomplete or incorrect information exchange. In negotiation situations that perceived advantage is in creating a better position. In conflict situations it is in avoiding a lesser position. Conflict resolution processes always have a more or less formal information exchange phase. Many conflicts are re-

solved as soon as more (or better) information becomes available to the parties (Saville-Smith, 2004).⁴⁴ Apparently, the conflict situation had frustrated information exchange, or the conflict was a result of a negotiation process where information exchange had been lacking, or was deceitful on purpose. The reason that information exchange is frustrated in conflict situations can be found in the perceived advantage in incomplete information exchange, combined with the emotional, competitive factors. A party in a conflict tends to be very careful not to provide the opponent with ‘ammunition’. At the same time there is an urgent need to express feelings of frustration. As a result the easiest way to debate is not to exchange information on the subject matter, but to provide opinions on the characteristics of the opponent, or exchange information aimed at influencing the relationship or the way communication takes place. The result of this is an increase in the number of, or the severity of, the emotional “links” that are created. The result of that is a further frustration of information exchange, and the conflict escalates. In conclusion, no conflict is ever started without information exchange, and none is resolved without it either.

⁴⁴ This study surveyed the impact of ADR on “traditional” litigation, and analyzed both quantitative and qualitative data. It was observed that especially lawyers had the experience that the best point in time to attempt ADR in a procedure that has been filed is after the discovery process is completed, ie at the point in time where the parties have been informed of the factual basis of the dispute.

V A FORMAL CONFLICT LANGUAGE

A. DEFINITION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN ELEMENTS

Many different theories about conflict exist, each using its own approach and terminology. Additionally, language itself has a flexible character, with words that have a range of different meanings and uses. As a result there is considerable ambiguity in the use of words and concepts. It is necessary to create a precise meaning of words and use of language when the objective is to create information technology to assist in conflict resolution. In other word, the structure of conflict must be understood and defined, or at least an attempt must be made to introduce a formal language to describe conflict structures, in order to improve understanding. This paper introduces conflict as a form of communication, aimed at achieving specific goals. Therefore, the definition of the proposed formal language starts from a communication model perspective.

The following diagram, representing a communication and relations/influences model, introduces some of the basic components of this proposed formal language, that will be used to describe the operation of the conflict models that will be developed. It shows the relationship between “agents”, “objects” and “objectives”, in a communication setting.

It is proposed that the formal language that will be presented in this paper can be used to capture the essential elements of conflict communication in an unambiguous way. If conflict resolution professionals would embrace the use of such a language to describe conflicts in the methodology that is provided, a theoretical basis to exchange conflict information may develop, which makes it possible to apply scientific methods that are found in the “hard sciences”.

Figure 4 An "objectives" communication model.

The arrows in this diagram represent “objectives”, which will be defined more formally, but at this point may be conceptualised as:

“a desire, action or statement with the objective to influence or chance the characteristics of the object it is aimed at.”

The diagram is highly simplified, as it only depicts two agents in communication, and two other agent/objects. It must also be noted that the “objectives” have only been visualised for one agent in this communication space. The other agent would have the mirror image of these “objectives” available to it. The diagram shows the abbreviations for agents (A), objects (O) and objectives (Q) that will

be used. There are further classifications and identifications within these main model components, which will be clarified below, and which lead to the additional letters in subscript and superscript. As an example, the subscript “ k ” (the ‘identifier’) denotes a number to identify an element within a range of similar elements, hence “agent one” would be written as A_1 , and “Object five” as O_5 .

A party to a conflict is a specific type of agent, which is indicated by the superscript “ P ”. Hence, “party agent one” would be abbreviated as A_1^P , and “relationship object seven” would be O_7^R .

The diagram represents the proposition made before, that any communication is aimed at substantive issues, but also at relationship issues and the communication setting as such. The communicating agents (ie the parties) are shown to have a relationship, which also effects the communication space between them. This relationship will be defined by means of relationship objects (O^R), and can be influenced by the parties in a direct or indirect manner. Indirect influence is exercised by means of another agent or object. As an example, conflicting agents in an organisational setting could seek to effect the relationship between them by involving a common superior, (another agent), or by using a status symbol, (an object). A direct influence to the relationship can take place overtly or concealed. Therefore there is one “objective arrow” that travels through the communication space (overt objective), and one outside of it (covert objective). To stay with the example, one party could communicate to the other “*I will see the boss about that*”, or this could be done without notification.

Similarly, the communication setting itself is influenced by what are called “formalities objects” (O^F). These can also be influenced directly or indirectly and overtly or covertly. Formality objects regulate the way the parties interact. The communication setting can be an informal conversation via telephone, or an exchange

in a court room. The formality objects include the communication infrastructure, protocols etc.

It is proposed that this highly abstract approach can accurately describe a communication effort, including the impact of relationship (power) characteristics. It also includes reference to the substantive issues about which the parties are communicating, by introducing objects and agents, which in turn have an impact on the relationship between the parties, or on the communication settings between them.

Some examples may clarify this diagram:

If the two “agents” at either side of the communication space are defined as parties to a contract about an object, the diagram can show the communications between them and the subsequent objectives aimed at the object in question. Contracting parties communicate about their relationship and adjust this relationship during the formation of their contract. For instance they could create a relationship whereby agent A_1^P repairs the car (object) of agent A_2^P . Once A_1^P undertakes the related action (a type of objective O^D), the relationship changes, A_1^P has performed and now A_2^P has to undertake an action aimed at the object ‘money’ to change the relationship again, hopefully to that of mutually satisfied supplier and customer. It can be seen that the objects in question (the substantive issue of the car repair and the payment) influence the relationship, which then effects the communication space.

It has been seen that not all objectives pass through the communication space itself, i.e. they are overt or covert. This is not a typical characteristic of conflict communication. Any communication will have that characteristic, but the choice between overt and covert objectives and the use of relationship characteristics (“power”) and formalities varies. This creates the distinction between ‘normal’ communication and conflict. As there are an infinite num-

ber of variations possible, no clear distinction between the two can be made, and there exist an endless number of “shades” of conflict.

The power characteristics of communication do not necessarily follow directly from the relationship between the parties, although power is a characteristic of a relationship, and not a characteristic of individual parties, as has been seen above. Politics would provide a good example of what is meant by a “power-based” communication, where influences outside of the direct relations between parties (indirect objectives) and outside of the communication environment (concealed objectives), play a vital role. A good example where the power structure is directly organised in the relationship itself and is very overt, would be a military environment. In that environment the relationship parameters are strictly defined to such an extent that they can be represented by simple coloured strips on the collar of the communicating “agents”.

The various components of this abstract model can now be formally introduced:

1 Objects (O)

Communication objectives relate to “objects”. Objects will be noted with the letter “*O*”. Additionally, for the purpose of clarity in this text, there is an object type indicator “ μ ” for the type of object, as was briefly introduced above. This indicator “ μ ” is the general term, which will be replaced by specific letters for the different types of objects that will be used. In the case of the objectives the number of different types has now been restricted to three, indicated by (*F*), (*M*) and (*R*), which will be described below. (μ) will therefore have the value (*F*), (*M*) or (*R*). These category indicators are notated in superscript. In the practical application, there will also be the (sub-

script) indicator (k) for a numerical identifier.⁴⁵ This results in the notation O_k^μ for any object. The identifier (k) is not important for this text and will therefore mostly be omitted.

At this stage, three types (μ) of objects (O) are identified, or formally:

$$(O_k^\mu, \mu \in \{F, M, R\}).$$

First the substantive objects ($\mu=M$), O^M , which can be anything, such as physical objects in dispute, money, an amount of time at a given date, an activity, the location of something, a relationship with another (non party) agent etc. The assumption is that substantive objects can be described with sufficient precision, and that their relevant qualities can be determined and measured with sufficient, and objective accuracy, hence the term “substantive”. An example is the car from the previous scenario, which can be described specifically, together with the relevant characteristics in that case, being the repairs, which have to be undertaken according to certain specifications.

Secondly, relationship objects ($\mu=R$), which will be called relations objects, O^R . These objects are the relationship parameters between parties themselves. The type of relationship will determine the variables that are necessary to describe that relationship. As indicated in the diagram the relations objects influence the communication environment, and have a direct and substantial influence on the parties. In the car repair example the relationship first changed from that of a customer enquiring about repairs to that of an offeror and an offerree. It then became a contractual relationship, followed by that of a satisfied customer and supplier. The characteristics of the repairs (i.e. time, conformity with specifications, and expressed

⁴⁵ Strictly speaking, the identifier “ μ ” is redundant, and could be retrieved from the database if the identifier “ k ” is known. Its use is aimed at keeping the formal nota-

as changes in the “object”) and the characteristics of the payment (i.e. time and quantity) have a direct impact on this relationship.

Thirdly, procedural objects, to be called formalities objects O^F ($\mu = F$). These contain the procedural parameters for the communication or conflict environment, and therefore substantially influence that environment. In the example: was the contract in written form, do the parties communicate directly about any problems, or is the matter subject of proceedings in a dispute tribunal, a mediation, or perhaps even a court? Different circumstances influence the way communication takes place.

It is assumed that all objects can be described satisfactorily and that their attributes and the values of those attributes can be determined and measured in one way or another. Eventually, a conflict is terminated by describing or determining a matrix of all relevant objects and the parties' relations to them, so this must always be a presumption that underlies the concept of dispute resolution.⁴⁶ In the repair example, if there was a conflict about the quality of the repairs, the conflict can be terminated by specifying an action to be undertaken by the garage, bringing that up to the required standard (a relationship between the garage and the object “car”). Alternatively it can be terminated by reducing the amount to be paid (a relationship between the customer and the object “money”). In both alternatives the end situation is a complex description of what has to be done by each party to change the relationship status from conflict to a more or less neutral position.

Objects will have a (potentially very large) number of ‘dimensions’, by which they are described, and each dimension can assume different ‘values’. The number of dimensions necessary to describe

tion understandable in written text.

⁴⁶ In the absence of the historically available, but no longer accepted alternative of terminating the opponent, rather than the conflict.

an object will depend on the character and factual matrix of the conflict, and the object at issue. The ‘state’ of an object is represented by all its ‘dimensions’ “ d ” and their value “ v ” at a given point in time “ t ”. There will be a range of dimensions with their associated values, so these will require identifiers as well, for which the subscript (i) is used. The ‘state’ of an object with x dimensions, at time $t=y$ is therefore completely described by the following notation:

$$O'_k = \sum_{i=1}^{i=x} O_k^{[\mu, d_i, v_i, (t=y)]}$$

This represents that the object state consists of the total description of the values of all the dimensions of the object at time (y).

An example in the family dispute arena would be an object that is described as a “visitation arrangement for a child”. Dimension one (d_1) could be “number of hours per week”, with a value of say “4”, and dimension two (d_2) could be “number of holiday weeks”, with a value of say “2”. One party could seek a change in the current object state to 6 hours per week and three weeks of holiday time. If it is assumed that this is the fifth object in dispute and the party seeks to change that situation by December 2005, than this objective could be written in this shorthand as:

$$O_5^{d_1=4, d_2=2, t=now} \Rightarrow O_5^{d_1=6, d_2=3, t=december2005}$$

An object itself will be indicated by O , while reference to an object state will be indicated generally by O' , and specifically by providing values for (d), (v), and (t), as shown in the example above. As indicated before, it will not be necessary to always include the identifier “ k ” or the various indicators or dimensions. They can be omitted where irrelevant.

The state of an object varies constantly, either by itself, or as a result of actions of agents. Furthermore, agents can describe their

objectives relating to objects in terms of a desired change in object state. In the car repair example, the customer will describe its objective as the change in the state of the car from “defect” to “fixed”, and that change is described by means of the various dimensions and their value, for instance “oil filter” from “old” to “new”. The garage will describe its objective as the receipt of an amount of money.

That a change in the state of an object between two points in time (omitting the indicators that are irrelevant in this context), takes place, can be represented as follows:

$$O^{',(t=2)} \neq O^{',(t=1)}$$

This expresses that the object state at two different points in time is different. The exact difference is described by the different values (v) for the relevant dimensions (d).

It is proposed that in a ‘general’ text, such as this paper, the type indicator (μ) is used where it is relevant to improve readability, although in automated systems this indicator will follow from the identifier “ k ”, and is not strictly necessary. This requires of course that all objects (O) are numbered sequentially, and that no separate number ranges are used for the different types of objects. In describing real conflict situations, it is recommended to also use the identifier (k) or a description of the object, in subscript notation, as soon as objects in dispute have been identified or indexed. The related values for dimensions (d) and values (v) are of course recorded in the CADR system, and can be used as necessary. The writing convention for the use of an object or object state description in text is therefore:⁴⁷

$$O_{|k|}^{[| |(F, M, R)| |d_i| |v_i| |t=x|]}$$

Many conflict situations, especially legal conflicts, are concerned with more or less standardized relationship objects (O^R). Further research will be necessary in which these are described and defined. For these O^R standardized “masks” can be developed, in which the relevant dimensions (d) and possible values (v) for these O^R are recorded. The car repair situation provides an example, were the parties engage in a contractual relationship. That relationship has legal consequences, and it arises only when certain criteria have been met. Another example is a tort situation, where the presence of an O^R , (in that case a “duty of care”) is one of the factors that determine whether a party (A_1^P) is liable to another (A_2^P) for a change in one or more substantive object states (O^M)⁴⁸. These examples can be expanded after introduction of the “objectives” (Q).

2 Agents (A)

The concept of an agent (A) is introduced, which could theoretically be seen as a specific type of object, but the distinction between objects and agents will be maintained. An agent is defined as an individual or a group of individuals, (where it is not relevant to distinguish individual members of that group).⁴⁹ Parties to a conflict are agents, and so are other individuals or groups that have a direct or indirect relationship with the conflict, or with the parties. Agents also have a typology (μ) or formally:

$$(A^\mu, \mu \in \{P, Rg, St, W\})$$

They also have an identifier (k).⁵⁰ Just as objects, agents have a state (A'), which can be described in dimensions and related val-

⁴⁷ Note that the vertical bars indicate that items enclosed between them are elective, and that parentheses indicate that any one of the terms between them can be chosen.

⁴⁸ Which in that situation are referred to as “damages”.

⁴⁹ As an example: “the police” or “the government”.

⁵⁰ And the same remarks for using this annotation apply as were mentioned when describing the object (O) notation.

ues, and can vary over time. (d), (v), and (t). The types “Party” ($\mu=P$), “Stakeholder” ($\mu=St$), “Reference group” ($\mu=Rg$), and “Witness” ($\mu=W$) have at this point been identified.

The type “party” (A^P) will require no further elaboration.

A stakeholder (A^{St}) is defined as an agent who has an interest in the outcome of a conflict, without being involved in it as a party.

A reference group (A^{Rg}) is defined as an agent that has an interest in a party, but no direct interest in the outcome of the conflict. Examples would be groups of relatives or friends on which a party relies for advise or support, a trade union or organisation, a religious organisation of which a party is a member, a legal advisor etc. An A^{Rg} can have a large impact on conflict behaviour, such as in matrimonial disputes, where other family members of the disputants can play a vital (positive or negative) role. Interesting situations also arise where the parties have overlapping reference groups, such as in the case of disputes within sports clubs or religious communities.⁵¹

A witness (A^W) is an agent that has information about objects that are relevant to the conflict, but that does not necessarily have an interest in the conflict outcome or a party.

Agents can therefore have more than one type, which is directly relevant to a conflict resolution process. As an example, the information from an agent $A^{W/St}$ will have to be observed differently than that from an agent A^W , or an agent $A^{W/Rg}$.

In analogy with the objects, an agent or agent state description has the following format: $A_k^{\mu,d,v,t}$, and the writing conventions are:

⁵¹ The last example provides a type of dispute where the substantive issues (O^M), can sometimes be absolutely beyond objective determination, and outside what can be achieved by legal process altogether, such as the determination which party has the correct interpretation of a religious dogma.

$$A_{|k|}^{[|l|,|(P,Rg,St,W)|,|d_i|,|v_i|,|t=x|]}$$

Agents have dimensions that cannot be changed other than by the agent itself. A good example is an emotional dimension. Although it may be helpful to identify the dimension “happiness”, this of course escapes precise definition or objective measurement. This type of agent dimensions will therefore not be considered, other than as a result of changes in object states. In the car repair example, the object state change of the car from “broken” to “fixed”, within the parameters of the relations-object “contract”, will result in the customer being “happy” with this transaction, but that doesn’t make the customer happy in a general sense. These emotional parameters will therefore be captured in a different way, which will be addressed later.

3 *Objectives (Q)*

Conflicts arise out of social “interaction”, which is a concept that is too imprecise to use. It implies some dynamic ‘connection’ or ‘relation’ between agents and/or objects. These connections or relations that agents have with objects or other agents will be termed “objectives”. They typically relate to some desired or actual change in object or agent state (*O*’ or *A*’). These objectives will be labelled *Q*.

In the car repair example the customer had an objective towards an object (the car) which was aimed at changing its state from “broken” to “fixed”. In order to pursue that objective, another objective was formed towards another agent (the garage), in order to create a relationship object (contract), which would result in the desired change in the object state of the car. The garage is interested to engage in that type of relationship objects, because it has an economic

objective towards the object money. (One could visualise that as the object state of its bank account).

The word “objective” has some ambiguity; it can, for example be used to describe a stated goal, or the underlying motives. Furthermore, different types of objectives will be distinguished, and the (not directly observable) emotional elements of an objective will be separated from those elements of the objectives that can be ‘objectively’ observed. In this paper the word ‘objective’ is used in a very broad sense. It involves any action, goal or statement aimed at changing an object or an agent state (*O*’ or *A*’).

At this point the objectives aimed at other agents must be discussed in more detail. Such agent objectives are related to object-oriented objectives, and in fact often form the motive for them. In the car repair example, the garage may have an objective to make its customer happy with its service, which is to be achieved by performing the object related objectives (fixing the car) in accordance with the relationship object (the contract) that has been created. In that situation the agent-objective (to make the customer happy) is of a secondary nature, and will have little relevance in resolving any dispute that may arise.

In some conflict situations the agent-objectives can be the driving force behind object-objectives, but will often not be disclosed, or even recognised. In the matrimonial dispute example, there could be a court case about the increased visitation rights, where the party seeking that increase is more concerned with winning the dispute, and thereby generating some negative impact on the other party, than with the actual object-objective of the increased rights. Dispute resolution in those situations may not be possible without identifying and discussing that type of objectives as well.

As recognised above, the problem with objectives aimed at agent states is that emotional agent states cannot be changed other

than indirectly, through other object states, and then only by an agent itself. Agent states can therefore not be the subject of objectives as they have been defined here. However, because they result from, or relate to, object-objectives the emotional component can be captured in the object oriented objectives. This emotional component will be described separately, as an ‘emotional binding’.

That means that objectives (Q) will only be considered insofar as they are aimed at changing object states (O'), and not where they are aimed at agent states (A'), which will have to be captured elsewhere.

The objectives Q also have types (μ) and identifiers (k), but they do not have dimensions and related values, as these are captured in the subject object states (O') and emotional bindings (B), which will be described below. Objectives can change over time, and will therefore have a time parameter t . The three types that have been identified at this point are actions ($\mu=D$), goals ($\mu=G$) and statements ($\mu=S$), or formally:

$$(Q^\mu, \mu \in \{D, G, S\})$$

In analogy with the objects and agents, an objective therefore has the format: $Q_k^{\mu,t}$

In descriptive text the objective type (the value for μ) can be added in superscript for clarity, as well as the related object and its type. It may sometimes be helpful to add the identifier for the party, this is proposed to be included as a subscript. The writing convention is therefore:⁵²

$$Q_{[k|A_i]}^{[(D,G,S)|,(O^F,O^M,O^R)|,t]}$$

⁵² And as with the other elements, any identifier or indicator can be omitted where it is not required.

As mentioned, an objective (Q) is thought to consist of a desired object state, and an emotional component. The emotional component captures those components of an objective that cannot be measured or determined objectively, and which are often even too complicated for a party itself to describe accurately. These emotions can relate to the emotional value of an object, such as a relationship, but it can also be the result of a desire to influence the emotional state of another agent, typically the other party. As a result of this complexity, emotional components must therefore be included in an indirect way. For this emotional component of an objective, the word “binding” (B) will be used, which will have the parameters ‘motivation’, ‘emotion’, and ‘intention’ (“ m ”, “ e ”, “ n ”).

Intention (n) relates to the type of conflict behaviour, as will be discussed later. It describes the way in which a party attempts to achieve its goals in the conflict communication environment. Intention can be established by means of an analysis of conflict behaviour, or by means of instruments such as those used in psychological tests (i.e. questionnaires).

“Motivation” (m) is the basis on which the intention is founded. An example for a motivation would be a legal entitlement, a moral obligation, an equitable right, or simply the desire to overpower the opponent. It is proposed that motivation can be described by means of a classification, which can be more or less standardized. Further research is required to create such a classification system.

“Emotion” (e) will describe the strength of the emotional binding, and will be captured by a classification of emotions and a scale of strength, which must also be developed following further research. The ‘emotion’ variable itself will therefore require more than one dimension.

The other elements that have been described (Objects, Agents and Objectives), all carry a “time stamp” in the variable t . The emotional binding (B) is always related to a specific objective (Q), which carries its own value for t . It is therefore not necessary to give the emotional binding its own time variable (t). The emotional binding (B), will of course vary with the state of the related object (O), and with the character (type) of objective (Q^μ) itself. As a result, emotional bindings follow a notation format that is different from that of the elements described thus far. This is the result of the fact that the emotional binding does not have the different types ‘motivation’, ‘emotion’, ‘intention’, but these are the components that make up the emotional binding. Emotional bindings are always connected to specific objectives, and do not exist by themselves. Therefore they do not require separate identifiers, but are always linked to the related objective. This is annotated by adding the objective and its identifier in subscript. The objective type is included for ease of understanding. The composition of an emotional binding can be notated in a formulaic way as:⁵³

$$B_{Q_k^\mu} = e \circ m \circ n$$

It is now time to look at the objectives in more detail.

In order to define an ‘action’ (Q^D), the following statement is made:

“A change in an object state can, by definition, only result from an ‘action’ by an agent, no matter what that action was comprised of.”

This allows for actions, but also for omissions that result in a change in object state.⁵⁴ It requires that there must be either a voluntary ‘action’ by an agent, or an influence on an agent by another

⁵³ Where the operator symbol “ \circ ” stands for “composition”.

⁵⁴ As an example, “George has let the property fall in disrepair”.

agent, leading to an action, before an object state can change. An action therefore always results in a change in an object state.

A goal (Q^G) will be defined as a desired change in an object state. A goal may be disclosed or not, but the disclosure itself requires an additional objective, in the form of a statement (Q^S). Without such an additional objective goals remain privy to the relevant agent only.

A statement (Q^S) will be defined as an information exchange, expressing an object state (O'), which can be a goal statement or any other object related information.

The purpose of defining these various types of objectives is to create a structure which will make it possible to capture information exchange between parties from the perspectives of the relevant objects, but also divided in information that is exchanged via statements or otherwise, and their related goals. Although goals are not always disclosed (probably mostly not), another agent will form an opinion about the goals underlying another party's statements and actions. This will lead to perceived objectives, and this will be addressed below.

An objective does not arise by itself. There must be a motivation, which is captured by the emotional component of an objective. It can be seen that an objective (Q), is the composition of an emotional binding that an agent has with a certain object state. This can be expressed in the following general notation:

$$Q_{k,A_i}^{\mu,t} = B_{Q_k^\mu} \circ O_k'$$

As the emotional binding itself cannot be described in objective terms, it follows that an objective can be described in terms of an object state only. It must be observed that the different type of objectives (Q^μ), although they may relate to the same object or object state can be formed under different emotional bindings, which

may lead to differences in the related object state. An example would be a goal (Q^G), which expresses a more modest object state than a related statement (Q^S), because the emotional component includes a certain amount of “negotiation” margin. In the matrimonial dispute example the following objectives could be present:⁵⁵

$$Q_{1,A_1}^G = B_{Q_1^G} \circ O_5^{d_1=6, d_2=3, t=december2005}$$

$$Q_{2,A_1}^S = B_{Q_2^S} \circ O_5^{d_1=8, d_2=4, t=december2005}$$

The stated goal (visitation rights for 8 hours/week and 4 weeks in the holidays, starting in December 2005) is different from the actual goal (6 hours, 3 weeks and the same start date), as it is formed under the influence of a different emotional binding, which included some negotiation margin.

Action objectives (Q^D) are formed in a similar way, under their own relevant emotional binding (B). As the diagram in figure 4 demonstrates, the difference between action and goal objectives on the one hand and statement objectives on the other is the route they take. Statement objectives always travel through the communication environment, as this is their purpose. As a result they are also subject to different emotional bindings. In other words, stated objectives are different from goal objectives because they are formed with a different purpose. (e.g. a realistic determination of entitlement versus a negotiation proposal). It will be noted that the action objectives have been kept outside the communication environment. This is a result of the earlier assumption that the communication content of actions will have to be considered separate from the action itself (that what changes an object state). As a result, an action objective will often result in a statement objective as well.

⁵⁵ Where the identifiers for Q have been inserted as random numbers. Note that the identifiers are numbered sequentially over all types of Q. Also the relevant

Furthermore, objectives can relate to agents just as well as to objects, but it has been discussed above that objectives aimed at the other party will not be considered, as they are assumed to be integrated in the emotional bindings. This leaves the question how objectives aimed at other agents can be treated. As the model shows, it is assumed that objectives aimed at other agents have the purpose to influence the other party and/or the communication formalities and/or the relationship between the parties. It is proposed to describe such agent-objectives in terms of the desired impact on relations- and formalities- objects, rather than in terms of a desired agent state, which is hoped to eventually bring the desired relations- or formalities- object state about. Where helpful, the indirect character of an objective, and the agent through which it is attempted to be achieved could be indicated. It is proposed to do that by adding the agent identifier in superscript and in brackets to the relevant object state that is to be achieved. The formal notation therefore becomes:⁵⁶

$$Q_{[k,|A_i]}^{[(D,G,S),|(A_m))|(O^F, O^M, O^R),|t]}$$

As a result, direct agent-objectives are not considered at all, but are either included in the emotional bindings, or are described by means of the object-objectives, which is the ultimate purpose of the agent-objective.

As stated, parties are a type of agents, while agents are in fact a specific category of objects. This complies with the abstract notion that from the perspective of one individual the entire external environment only consists of objects, with which different relationships

party has been annotated in accordance with the convention that has been introduced.

⁵⁶ Note that in the superscript agent the identifier “*m*” has been used. This is to indicate that this is of course another agent than the *A_i* in the subscript which indicates the party forming or expressing the objective, while the superscript *A_m* is the agent through which an indirect objective is pursued.

are maintained over time, varying from the very simple objectives such as consumption to complicated social cooperation structures. At this level of abstraction, a person's objectives can be reduced to the capacity of the objects to fulfil needs, structured in hierarchies such as those used by anthropologists (Maslow, 1970). Such an abstraction would allow using a concept where the relative strength of emotional bindings could be determined on the basis of the location of the related objectives in this hierarchy of needs. It is not proposed that such a concept has practical application at this point. Ultimately though, emotional bindings will be understood at this level of abstraction, perhaps even at a more abstract level, if more becomes known about the way emotions develop, and their impact on conflict development, and therefore, conflict management.⁵⁷

As a result of the definitions that have now been introduced, and the way the notations are constructed, conflict is always about objects, either 'substantive', 'relations', or 'formalities'. Therefore, issues in conflict also always relate to objects. As was stated before, the assumption is that objects can always be described and measured with sufficient accuracy and objectivity.⁵⁸ Emotional parameters have been included, but in such a way that they avoid the necessity to be described or measured in a direct way.

⁵⁷ It is even proposed that ultimately a biological approach to conflict management will be possible. The invitation for a symposium on "The biology of conflict management" organised by the international association of conflict management in June 2005, contains the following introduction:

"While conflict management has been emerging as a distinct professional practice and field of academic inquiry over the last several decades, there have been extraordinary advances in the biological sciences. Yet the potential contributions of biology and other so-called "hard sciences" to conflict management have been largely ignored by conflict management scholars and practitioners. Evolutionary theory is helping to develop better explanations of pro-social behaviours, the building blocks of conflict resolution. Meanwhile, technological breakthroughs in the neurosciences provide a window on brain and neuro-chemical functions that are associated with such behaviours. The Consortium on Negotiation and Conflict Resolution (CNCR) Nexus Project on Biology and Conflict Management is now examining the potential contributions of biology to the conflict management field.

⁵⁸ Which is an essential presumption of any dispute resolution or determination process. It would be useless to have such a process if the objects at issue cannot be described, or the outcome determined.

At this point the description of conflict issues can be formalised.

B. CLASSIFICATION OF CONFLICT ISSUES

Issues are the result of differences between the parties about (a number of) individual objects. These differences do not result from the mere existence of an object, but from incompatibility of parties' objectives (Q) related to an object (O). Issues arise when the parties' actions, statements or goals in relation to an object (the objectives, Q) are incompatible. This can mean that the Q of both parties is the same, and therefore incompatible, for instance in the case of scarce resources, where both parties' objectives cannot be satisfied out of the resource (e.g. a dispute about the ownership a specific car). But that is not necessarily so. The objectives can be very different but still incompatible (e.g. John wants to move to Australia with his wife Mary, who would rather be married to Bill).

For that reason a specific notation is introduced for compatibility ($\langle c \rangle$) and incompatibility ($\langle nc \rangle$) of objectives. An example of an issue formally described in that manner would be:⁵⁹

$$I = Q_{A_1} \langle nc \rangle Q_{A_2}$$

Or, in words: an issue equals (arises) where two parties' objectives are not compatible.

It can readily be seen that the incompatibility in reality lies at the level of the object states that are part of the conflicting objectives. It is therefore necessary to construct a notation to make it possible to describe the issues accurately.

⁵⁹ Under omission of unnecessary identifiers and indicators.

In analogy with the notations developed above, the categories of issues (I) will be labelled with a typology (μ), and an identifying numeral (k).⁶⁰

The typology (μ) is however somewhat more complicated than it is for the objects, agents and objectives (O, A, Q), as it is a composite indicator. This paper recognises three categories of objects: ($O^\mu, \mu \in \{F, M, R\}$), three categories of objectives ($Q^\mu, \mu \in \{D, G, S\}$), and four categories of agents ($A^\mu, \mu \in \{P, R_g, Th, W\}$). As observed, agents have the same morphology as objects, and objectives aimed at agents will not be described directly, and therefore need not be considered here.

Starting with the objectives; an issue can relate to objectives from the same category, which can be indicated in its (μ), as follows, for an issue about action objectives:

$$I^{DD} = Q_{A_1}^D <nc> Q_{A_2}^D$$

The indicator DD in subscript denotes that the issue is about two conflicting action objectives.

A reference to the parties (A_1 and A_2) has also been included to improve readability. (The identifiers (k) and other objective indicators have been omitted, as they are not relevant here, but can be included when describing a specific conflict situation). Issues can of course result from perceived objectives, which will be annotated by including an exclamation mark ($Q!$). The implications of that will be discussed in more detail below, but which would lead to the following notation for an issue resulting from one party's action objective and the other party's perceived action objective:

⁶⁰ And the same remarks for using this annotation apply as were mentioned when describing the object (O), agent (A), and objective (Q) notations.

$$I^{DD!} = Q_{A_1}^D < nc > Q_{A_2}^{D!}$$

Issues can be about different categories of objectives (Q^μ), and may or may not relate to perceived objectives, for example:

$$I^{SG!} = Q_{A_1}^S < nc > Q_{A_2}^{G!}$$

Which defines an issue about one party's statement objective (e.g. a stated goal) and another party's perceived goal objective.

By definition there cannot be an issue (I) that relates objectives (Q), which relate to different types of objects (O^μ).⁶¹ The reason is that the objectives would theoretically always be compatible. This is one of the concepts behind ADR, finding compatible objectives related to different objects or object types, to compensate for non-compatible objectives relating to the same object.

As a result the possible combinations in which issues can arise, and the resulting typology (μ) for this objective (Q) can be identified in the following table, which represents the issues from the perspective of part A_1 :

$A_1 \backslash A_2$	D	G	S	$D!$	$G!$	$S!$
D	DD	DG	DS	$DD!$	$DG!$	$DS!$
G	GD	GG	GS	$GD!$	$GG!$	$GS!$
S	SD	SG	SS	$SD!$	$SG!$	$SS!$

Table 1 Possible objective issue types I^μ , from party A_1 perspective

An additional classification arises out of the objects at issue. It is helpful to add these in the form of superscript capitals as it was

⁶¹ Remember that Q is composed of a binding and an object state, as was expressed in $Q = B \circ O'$

done with the objectives (i.e. O^M , O^R , O^F) so it is immediately clear what type of issue exists. As stated, for this purpose, agents can be seen as a category of objects, but which will be kept distinct, and only added as an indicator for an indirect objective. They will therefore not have to be included in the issue notation itself. The resulting writing convention for issues will therefore be:

$$I_{[k,|A_1]}^{[(DD, DG, DS, DD!, DG!, DS!, GD, GG, GS, GD!, GG!, GS!, SD, SG, SS, SD!, SG!, SS!)|(O^M, O^R, O^F)]}$$

Some further remarks must be made about the object types as they appear in the issues, which will provide some examples of the “language” that has now been developed.

1 Substantive issues, (“M” Object Issues)

Substantive objects issues I^{OM} arise when the parties’ actions, statements or goals in relation to an object (the objectives, Q) are incompatible, as described above. In practical application, references to the actual objectives at issue are required, leading to the general notation:

$$I_k = Q_l < nc > Q_m$$

Here l and m are variables that provide the links to the objectives (Q), and thereby to the relevant binding (B) and object state (O) descriptions, and all further underlying information. In general text, such as this, these variables are not relevant and will be omitted. To make the annotation more readable the references to the objective and object types have been included in the writing convention. As an example:

$$I_{k, A_1}^{GD!, O^M} = Q_{l, A_1}^{G, O^M} < nc > Q_{m, A_2}^{D!, O^M}$$

This would stand for an issue as perceived by party A_1 , about a substantive object, between parties A_1 and A_2 , which has arisen out of party one's non-disclosed goal not being compatible with a perceived action by party two. As an example, party one has the goal objective to have a property transferred from party two, but perceives that party two is not willing to effect that transfer.

The 'magnitude' of an issue can be quantified by determining the difference between the parties' objectives, (in the following example in the form of statements) or:⁶²

$$\|I^{SS,O^M}\| = Q_{A_1}^{S,O^M} - Q_{A_2}^{S,O^M}$$

This issue can also be described using the parties' actual goals, which is likely to be different from the stated goals:

$$\|I_{k,A_1}^{GG,O^M}\| = Q_{l,A_1}^{G,O^M} - Q_{m,A_2}^{G,O^M}$$

There can be a substantial difference in the 'magnitude' of a dispute ($\|I\|$) as stated and as actually present, representing the amount of 'posturing', or "negotiation gap", and which would follow from:

$$\|I^{SS,O^M}\| - \|I^{GG,O^M}\|$$

The same result would be found by adding the differences in the goal and statement objectives of each party individually, or in formula:

$$\|I^{SS,O^M}\| - \|I^{GG,O^M}\| = \left\| \left(Q_{A_1}^{S,O^M} - Q_{A_1}^{G,O^M} \right) + \left(Q_{A_2}^{S,O^M} - Q_{A_2}^{G,O^M} \right) \right\|$$

⁶² Where the double bars stand for the magnitude or size of an issue. The minus sign indicates that the objectives are compared to find the magnitude of the issue as the difference between the parties' objectives. Note that irrelevant indicators and identifiers have been omitted in this example.

The difference in Q^S and Q^G is of course found by comparing the object states O in the S- and G-condition, and the equation could be re-written as:⁶³

$$\|I^{SS,O^M}\| - \|I^{GG,O^M}\| = \left\| \left(O_{Q_k,A_1}^{M,d,v} - O_{Q_l,A_1}^{M,d,v} \right) + \left(O_{Q_m,A_2}^{M,d,v} - O_{Q_n,A_2}^{M,d,v} \right) \right\|$$

The object state differences relate only to the effect of the emotional binding B in the conditions Q^S and Q^G , which follows from the equation $Q = B \circ O$.

In other words: the total amount of ‘posturing’ or ‘negotiation gap’ in a conflict equals the total of the differences between the effects of emotional bindings in statement and goal conditions for both parties. It would follow that removing or reducing the effect of the emotional component between the parties decreases the absolute magnitude of an issue, and thereby the magnitude of the conflict. This would increase the chance of resolution. This is directly borne out by the success of e-settlement, e-negotiation etc.

2 Relationship issues (“R” Objects Issues)

Relationship issues describe incompatibilities in relationship objectives between the parties. A relationship objective has the same logical structure as the other objectives, as a result of the definitions already provided. As an example, a relationship goal is formed by $Q^{G,O^R} = B \circ O^{R}$, but could be stated as $Q^{S,O^R} = B \circ O^{R}$, with the magnitude $\|Q^{G,O^R} - Q^{S,O^R}\|$, as a measure of tactics. Issues arise where the parties’ relationship objectives are not compatible.

⁶³ Note that the objectives have been added in subscript to the related objects to remain clarity, although this will not be necessary in an automated system as these follow from the identifiers.

Relationship issues typically involve an associated (unequal) relationship power distribution. Examples can be parent-child or supplier-customer. Often relationship issues arise indirectly, as a result of relationships the parties have with objects outside the dispute environment. This is especially the case where some external relationship with a resource influences the power distribution between the parties. A simple example is the relationship with money. If one party has a significant relationship with money, and the other not, this may have relevance to the conflict, by influencing relationship or formalities objects O^R and O^F . If necessary such an external influence would have to be factored in, e.g. by recognising $Q_{O^M}^D$, where Q^D would be the (non) action objective “to possess”, and O^M would be the generic object “money”.⁶⁴ This type of relationship is depicted in the communication objectives diagram by the influence from an agent / object to the relationship objects. An alternative way of achieving this would be by creating the relationship object (O^R) “financial” with a dimension (d) “financial status compared” and value (v) options “relatively rich” or “relatively poor”, or whatever grading would be relevant. Both methods can be used simultaneously, whereby the second could be derived from the first, depending on other information available.

The other formal definitions are similar to those expressed above and need not be repeated.

3 Procedural issues (“F” Objects Issues)

The third group of issues relates to the communication formalities or conflict procedures. These issues must be kept separate from the substantive and relationship issues, as they can have no value or relevance outside of the conflict environment. Within that environ-

⁶⁴ Note that the related object O is added in subscript to the objective Q to aid readability.

ment they do play an important role and can eventually become a significant factor in conflict escalation by themselves, to be determined separately by third party interveners (Beck, 2001). (e.g. interlocutory decisions, choice of resolution process etc). The descriptions follow the examples given above. Again there is a relationship to formalities objects possible, which results from an objective aimed at an agent or object (an indirect objective).

At this point an example of grammatical and logic constructs can be given. Here the practical application, rather than the theoretical is simulated, to demonstrate the possibilities of the basic definitions provided thus far. The basic syntax of a sentence is always AQO , which stands for an agent A executing an objective Q , aimed at an object O . This may be compared with the basic syntax subject, verb, and object.

A somewhat numerical example is chosen to exemplify the working of the dimensions and their related values. Imagine the following three “sentences” describing, an information exchange, followed by an action and the resulting observed change in the value of one object dimension. The identifying numbers have been chosen randomly, as they only serve to provide references to information located elsewhere.

$$A_1 Q_{23} O_5^{t=1} \dots A_1 Q_{38} O_5^{t=2} \dots A_6 Q_{125} O_5^{t=3}$$

The identifiers would refer to the following data:

A_1 would include: $\mu=P$, and further links to information about the party.

Q_{23} would include: $\mu=G, O^M$; a link to O_5 , and $d(7)$ as relevant objective dimension, and $t1=1/5/04$

O_5 (in combination with Q_{23} , which provides a date) at $t1=1/5/04$ would include: $\mu=M$; $d(7)$ =fertilizer, part/m² ; $v=24$

Q_{38} at $t=26/6/04$ would include: $\mu=D$, and $t=26/6/04$, and reference to O_5 .

O_5 (in combination with Q_{38} , which provides a date) at $t=26/6/04$ would include: $\mu=M$; $d(7)=\text{fertilizer, part/m}^2$; $v=26$

A_6 would include: $\mu=W$, plus links to info, e.g. website.

Q_{125} would include: $\mu=S$, and $t=17/8/04$

O_5 (in combination with Q_{125} , which provides a date)at $t=17/8/04$ would include: $\mu=M$; $d(7)=\text{fertilizer, part/m}^2$; $v=22$

Or in ‘meta’ language: “Agent one, a party to the dispute, makes statement (numbered 23), conveying a goal, relating to the 7th dimension of a substantive object (object no. 5), and providing a value of 24”. This statement is followed by an action of that party (numbered 38), with the objective to change that value to 26. The result is that the actual value is changed to 22, as was observed and stated by a witness.”

This meta-language could be the result of analysing the following correspondence:

“As I informed you on 1 May 2004, the required level of nitrogen in the soil should be 24part/m². On 26 June 2004 I have applied fertiliser, which I thought should have brought the level to 26part/m². However, the result when measured by M.A.F on 17 August 2004 was 22part/m².”

The structure of this ontology can be relatively simply made to comply with a semantic web” approach, for instance the one proposed in CRML, Conflict Resolution Modelling Language (Hendler, 2004).⁶⁵ Logical descriptive sentences have the format:

single agent > single relation > single object

Which compares with subject, verb, object, complying with the basic structure that one object “possesses” another. It is this descrip-

⁶⁵ Although this paper introduces numerous additions and variations to CRML as a proposed RDF/RDFS application by Hendler.

tion of objects and relationships, which builds the semantic hierarchy. Such “atomic” sentences can be validated by a computer system. The addition of time as a variable allows for a much richer description of objectives, while the addition of statements to the proposed CRML structure will allow for the analysis of tactics. The additions in dimensions, values and typologies are at a different implementation level, and do not disturb the basic structure. They provide indications for the required database structure to create a practical application.

It will be seen that the purpose of defining a strict language to describe conflict will initially be aimed at translating conflict statements in ordinary language to a highly formalised language that can be used in a CADR system. Ultimately (when an appropriate ontology has been defined in detail) such a system should be independently able to analyse statements, whereby human intervention is necessary to make sure that logic is maintained, and that the factual information is related appropriately.

A practical demonstration of the potential of a semantic analysis approach can be provided by showing the graphical representation of a computer analysis of a reasonable number of documents produced in a real dispute. The following graph was produced by using a software tool that analyses text in order to retrieve important concepts. There was no user input at all. The program was simply provided with a number of files, containing MSWord documents and email messages. This software was not developed for the purpose of conflict resolution, but is mainly promoted to find concepts in large texts, such as books.

Figure 5 Concept map ⁶⁶

From this diagram it can be inferred that there are parties, an applicant and a number of respondents and that the issue between them relates to a caveat. The concepts ‘boundary’, ‘plan’ and ‘consent’ have been retrieved as important.

The following step involves another software tool that extracts ‘meta data’ from large numbers of documents, and graphically displays relationships between documents based on concepts that are entered by the user. Using some of the concepts that were retrieved in the first step, the following graph was produced, which provides a convenient way to relate documents that contain these concepts. The input into the system consisted of the same files that were used in the first step. Each dot represents a document that can be directly accessed using this ‘cluster map’. The map provides a convenient way of finding and retrieving relevant documents.

⁶⁶ Produced with Leximancer software, see www.leximancer.com

Figure 6 Cluster map ⁶⁷

It can be seen that an almost fully automated process did directly provide a relevant structure from an amount of documents that had as only organising principle that it was related to this dispute. Without reading any documents there would be a (albeit rough) determination of the apparent issues in dispute, and documents have been organised accordingly. Although it is admitted that this not yet provides the database or information structure that would be necessary to implement the conflict language that has been defined in this paper, it proves that various developments are taking place in different fields that can be brought together to assist in creating a new application such as the CADR system. This is exactly the concept behind the semantic web.

A formal definition of conflict language, as attempted in this project, would provide a way to enhance the accuracy of this type of tools by providing semantic structures and content for which the software can be programmed to look. Items such as dates, sender/receiver etc are extracted automatically, and a start can be made to populate a database of conflict information, which can be subsequently enhanced by the parties and the third party neutral.

⁶⁷ Produced with Autofocus 5.1, see www.aduna.biz.nl

VI STATIC MODEL OF CONFLICT

A. A DESCRIPTION OF THE STATIC MODEL

Early communication models tend to focus on the sender-receiver metaphor, and include the effect of intermediate, and situational sources of interference on the transmission (Shannon & Weaver, 1949). The later study of the influence of culture on negotiation and conflict was fuelled by increasing development of international business. It shifts the focus to models showing the influence of culture on the actors in the communication setting, rather than interpreting culture as an instance of “noise” in the transmission. This topic will be discussed in more detail below.

This paper proposes a static model that can be represented with the diagram in the following figure:

Figure 7 A static or 'snapshot' view of conflict

This diagram must be seen in conjunction with the “objectives” model as presented in the diagram in figure 4, although these diagrams are not strictly congruent. They approach the conflict setting from a different conceptual perspective. The objectives model

focuses on the objectives of the parties, including those aimed at influencing relationships and communication settings. The static model is concerned with the way environmental influences operate on the parties. The actions of the other party to the dispute are of course part of the environment. An approximate analogy would be to represent the static model as if it was reduced to a horizontal plane, and that the elements that are represented in the “objectives” diagram would be taken out of that plane, and represented on a different plane that intersects with the static model diagram. The “communication space” from the “objectives” model would in that case roughly coincide with the “conflict and conflict resolution environment” in the static model. A detailed description of the conceptual connection between these models is not relevant in this phase of the project, but the resulting construction can be represented in a three-dimensional diagram as the one that follows below.

This model represents the environmental factors operating on the parties (the horizontal planes), as well as (or including) influences, which are directly or indirectly generated by the other party to the conflict, as a result of that party’s objectives. The influences that operate from ‘within’ the party can be seen through the somewhat transparent spheres that represent the parties.

The objectives that are expressed are shown as coming through the communication space (the overt objectives) while the non-communicated objectives (the covert objectives) stay outside of the communication space.

The effect of the objectives has been discussed in chapter V, the remaining elements of the static model will be discussed by addressing the environment of conflict, the social psychology of conflict, and the place and role of conflict issues in the model.

Figure 8 A 3D presentation of objectives and static conflict models

As will be seen, the static model focuses on describing the influences on a party in a conflict situation, as these operate to eventually determine the conflict behaviour that a party uses during the conflict. It must be kept in mind however, that the objectives remain part of the static model, and are included at the level of each “snap-

shot” that is represented by this model. To provide an example: if the static model is described at the “snapshot” of a certain date, it would include the environmental influences that operate on the parties at that point in time, and it would include the effect of the objectives of both parties on one another, as they operate at that point in time.

B. THE ENVIRONMENT OF CONFLICT

Parties do not exist only in the conflict environment. They remain part of society and interact with it. There must have been some area where the interests or activities of the parties overlapped prior to the conflict, otherwise there could not have been a dispute. It remains also possible that they interact with each other outside the dispute situation. Once dispute resolution is undertaken a different environment can be recognised, with rules and procedures and environmental influences of its own.

It is proposed that using overall environmental influences is insufficiently accurate. Therefore a distinction between four different environments is suggested, with an increasing intensity as their characteristics concentrate on the dispute environment as a subset of the total environment. As an example, if the dispute resolution environment is a court hearing, than that environment places real restrictions on the way parties operate. In a typical court hearing the environmental influence is so strong that the parties themselves don’t operate at all.

This “narrowing down” of the environment towards the resolution environment is represented by the ‘concentric’ subsets of the total environment. The diagram shows an “entire environment” within which an ‘interaction environment’ is indicated, of which the “conflict environment” is a subset. The type of dispute (e.g. contract

or tort) will define the boundaries between the ‘entire’ and the ‘interaction’ environment.

Within the conflict environment there can be a separate environment for dispute resolution. This is a subset of the conflict environment, where other rules may apply, other participants are introduced etc. Logically, both parties are deemed to be present in all environments, with a decreasing subset of their activities, but with an increased intensity. Recognition of the different environments in which the parties operate is relevant for the application of “field theories”, which seek to describe the influence of the environment on the development and operation of conflict.

A conflict develops in the interaction environment, escalates in the conflict environment, and over time will come to a resolution in the most restricted of those environments. There is a relationship between the various conflict stages and the environment of the conflict. If it is the objective to capture the development of conflict in an analytical tool, to be used for dispute resolution, the influence of these different environmental impacts must be recognised. Although this may appear quite irrelevant from the perspective of a judge in court hearing, other resolution processes, such as transformative mediation, are highly interested in the (prior) relationships between parties in other than the conflict environment.

1 The entire environment

The entire environment represents the total external environment as relevant for both parties. A description of this environment is not necessary. Recognition of the effect of influences from this environment (e.g. law) is sufficient. As an example, it is public policy that parties should be encouraged to resolve disputes without having to refer to litigation. As long as the direct consequences of that influence are represented in the model, the policy itself is irrelevant.

In this example this will mean that discovery and confidentiality procedures used in the system must be made to comply with this external influence, and that the parties must be assisted to achieve this while using the system. Any agent (*A*) or object (*O*) that is relevant to the conflict, is considered to be part of the conflict environment, and will be defined there, no matter how remote its influence is.

2 *The interaction environment*

The interaction environment is the subset of the entire environment that describes the setting in which the parties interact. Only a section of the parties is included in the interaction environment, whereas they interact with the entire environment outside that area. The interaction environment will have specific characteristics that can be described at an increased level of detail. An example of a general characteristic of that setting could be “commercial”, “service provider – client”, “partners in partnership” etc. The description of this environment provides the direct background in which the relationship between the parties and their dispute has developed. Different interaction environments create different assumptions, expectations, norms and criteria for operation. This is relevant for the application of both process rules and legal assumptions. If the parties have very different opinions about the parameters of their interaction environment, this may be an important source of substantive, but also emotional differences about the issues in dispute. The interaction environment is not the same as the conflict environment. Parties may have evolved their conflict to include their total interaction environment, they may even be using the conflict to expand the interaction environment, but that is not necessarily the case. It is possible that parties have a large interaction environment in which the dispute only represents a small area. Issues may move between the interaction and the conflict environment. One way of resolving dispute is to resolve individual issues, thereby contracting the conflict area and

possibly increasing the transaction area (a win-win resolution). The opposite is also possible, where the dispute expands, thereby moving items from the “neutral” part of the interaction environment to the conflict environment. This can relate to further substantive issues, but also to procedural issues. An example of the latter can be found in interlocutory proceedings. In that case the dispute may grow as a result of its own dynamics, increasing the emotional component without any benefit to resolution.

3 *The conflict environment*

The conflict environment is a subset of the interaction environment. It contains that part of the parties’ interactions about which they consider to be in conflict. It will be important for any dispute resolution process that the parties have a similar understanding about the distinction between the characteristics of the interaction and the conflict environment, and the dimensions of the conflict environment as a subset of the interaction environment. Discrepancies in that perception can be a source of conflict itself, which may be removed by accurate description of the conflict environment. As the dispute resolution literature shows, conflict description is an essential part of many resolution processes. The formal adjudication processes simply cannot operate without an appropriate description of the conflict environment, albeit that that description is restricted to a limited number of parameters (i.e. legal entitlements and their factual matrix only). On the one hand, that is an advantage of formal processes, as they concentrate on those facts that are relevant for the determination of legal questions that arise in the dispute. On the other hand, however, this is considered one of the handicaps of formal processes, as they lack the flexibility to look beyond legal entitlements. (Or put in another way, outside the border of the conflict resolution environment).

4 *The dispute resolution environment*

It is important to realise that this resolution environment is often a relatively small subset of the total conflict environment. The representation of the reference group and culture influences (the two smaller ellipses) in the model indicates the assumption that these influences continue in the resolution environment. The operation of cultural influences will depend on the impact of the environment influences, and the question if a party is represented in the resolution environment. If that is the case, cultural influences of the advocate will play a role, although those are normally restricted by influences of the resolution environment. If a stricter resolution environment is used, the restraint on cultural influences increases. The ultimate example is the process in appeal courts, where the environmental restraints exclude virtually all impact of emotional, group or cultural influences from the proceedings. The reference group influences (the intermediate ellipse) extend into the resolution environment as well, but their character also necessarily changes. An example of that is found in confidentiality rules. Where a party may be free to discuss matters with a member of his reference group, restrictions apply as soon as the resolution environment is entered into.

C. *THE SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY OF CONFLICT*

As observed before, conflict has a social function. Yet the impact on the parties themselves, whether they are individuals or organisations, may not be underestimated. Conflict leads to strong sentiments, which are capable of completely overshadowing any rational motive behind the conflict. Social psychologists refer to this emotional process as “entrapment” (Brockner & Rubin, 1985). Although complete entrapment represents an extreme, all conflict situations are characterised by an important emotional component, which is what sets them apart from ordinary communication situations.

Psychologists recognise a myriad of definitions of the concept emotion. An inventory found 150 different theories (Strongman, 1996). In the conflict context, ‘emotions’ must be seen as being different from ‘moods’, which represent a more general state of mind of an individual. This paper uses the widely accepted notion, which holds that ‘emotions’ and ‘moods’ are differentiated by the degree to which affective states (emotions) are more or less directed towards specific situational stimuli (which can include people, things, events, etc). Or, as it is put:

*“Emotions are about, or directed toward, something in the world...”*⁶⁸

Emotions lead to motivations and behaviour. A theory must be included that provides for description and analysis of these emotional factors. It is theorised that parties create emotional bindings (B) with objects (O) in dispute, resulting in actions, goals, and statements (Q). Emotions are treated as a component (e) of the emotional binding (B). These bindings will reflect the relative importance of the substantive issues, and the evaluation of that importance against various other criteria, including relationship issues. Conflict strategies (i.e. the sum of all goal-objectives, or ΣQ^G) are chosen on the basis of one party’s perception of the other’s party’s intention ($n!$) to cooperate⁶⁹ (Sillars, 1980). The objects at issue in the dispute are a part of the static conflict model, by inclusion of the object states in the construction of parties’ objectives (Q). In figure 4 a diagram was presented that demonstrated influences that effect the emotional bindings and the related conflict behaviour. That representation is of course restricted to the influences between the parties and/or other agents or objects. The environmental influences have been dis-

⁶⁸ Parrot (2001) as quoted by Barry, Fulmer and Van Kleef, in (Gelfand & Brett, 2004), pg72.

⁶⁹ Or rather: the perception of the expected conflict behaviour generally.

cussed above; we must now turn to other social psychological factors.

The concept used is that a party operates under three ‘spheres’ of personal influences in a conflict situation.

The influences on each disputant are represented by a set of partly nested ellipses. This represents that a party, although appearing as a ‘closed’ entity, is in fact operating under a number of influences that are more or less external to it, but which are not apparent to the casual observer. This can be seen as forces that are acting within a party’s emotional operation at a given point in time. The representation in the diagram attempts to visualise those influences that ultimately lead to conflict behaviour.

1 The disputant’s internal influences

The outer ellipse represents the “entire” party itself. Included in this ellipse are the party’s views, standpoints, emotions, information, and all other relevant “internal” influences, which eventually result in the emotional bindings (*B*). These “internal” influences are in continuous state of flux. With every event that occurs a new evaluation is made in which matters are “internalised” or not. Only “internalised” events will eventually lead to actions or changes in behaviour. Nevertheless, cognitive dissonance studies have shown that forced behaviour or discrepancies between desired and achievable goals will eventually lead to adjustment in the way individual motivations operate (Brewer & Crano, 1994).

In this paper these influences are termed “internal influences”, whereby no distinction is made depending on their origin. All internal influences together can be described as the “psychological” dimension, and are described in theories such as the psychodynamic⁷⁰

⁷⁰ Developed by Freud, Adler, Sullivan, Rapaport and others, see (Folger *et al.*, 2005), p45-46.

approach, cognitive dissonance theory, the part of verbal aggressiveness theory that looks at verbal aggressiveness as part of personal traits (Folger *et al.*, 2005), argumentativeness (Infante & Wigley, 1986), and attribution theory (Sillars, 1980).

Some of these personal characteristics may find their way into relevant dimensions and values (d, v) of the agent “party” (A^P), and become subject to the other party’s objectives in relation to their state (A'). However, this will be the exception rather than the rule, and such direct party-oriented objectives have been excluded from the formal conflict language definitions that were introduced in chapter V.

2 Reference group influences

The second, smaller, ellipse represents the presence of the ‘group’ relationships of a party (Franzoi, 1996; Kramer, 2004). This group will be termed the “direct group of reference or reference group” in this paper, while the influences exerted by this group on the party will be termed “reference group influences”. These influences can be divided in reference influences arising from agents that have no interest in the dispute itself and those that do. Agents that provide reference, and have an interest in the outcome of the dispute can be termed stakeholders. These are individually recognised as an agent type (A^{St}). Additionally there is an agent type “reference group” (A^{Rg}) available where that is relevant, i.e. where one party to a conflict has objectives to influence the relationship between the parties or the procedural settings of the conflict environment by influencing the other party’s reference group.

It is important to note that the reference influences can be positive or negative. It is equally important to note that these actors operate through the party and have no direct role in the conflict. This is why the term “third parties” is carefully avoided in this context, and

is reserved for those actors that have a direct role in the dispute. As a result of this definition, a stakeholder can change into a third party, and a combined role is also possible. Given the restrictions formulated for this research, third parties in the strict sense are not considered, but the influence of actors that operate as combined stakeholders/third parties cannot be avoided.⁷¹ A specific situation arises where the parties are both significantly related to the same reference group (A^{Rg}). In that circumstance the reference group becomes a potential determinant for the conflict communication environment, possibly also as a determinant of formalities objects (O^F). That would specifically be the case where the conflict has arisen in the course of participation in this reference group. (e.g. a dispute between fellow ornithologists and members of the Forest and Bird society, in a dispute about naming rights to a new species of seagull).

3 *Cultural influences*

The smallest ellipse represents the influence of the ‘culture’ on the disputant. This is the cultural background from which a party operates. The culture influence is drawn partly overlapping the group reference ellipse, as there is overlap between cultural and direct group influences, but the culture component operates differently. It contains the values, norms and belief system of the disputant. Reference group influences will be direct and to some extent directly relevant to the dispute, while cultural influences will operate in the background, and are largely concealed for the party itself as well, as a party itself will not consciously apply cultural influences (Hofstede, 1984). It has been argued (Avruch, 1998) that cultural differences have a direct correlation with conflict behaviour, and this appears to be borne out by research (Ozcelik, 2005).

⁷¹ Following directly from this analysis is the conclusion that in a multi-party conflict, the possible relationships between the parties (coalitions) play an important role. A model for multi party dispute would require representations for all possible constellations of such coalitions.

The cultural influences are extended into the dispute resolution area, as a party cannot abandon its cultural reference. It must be noted that in representative dispute resolution environments this influence is minimised, and partly replaced by that of the representative, which provides an example of the impact of the environmental factors of the dispute resolution environment. In that circumstance the cultural influence that played a role in the development of conflict is removed from the resolution process.

The impact of culture on communication can be represented in a diagram. A basic example (Victor, 1992), consists of two partly overlapping circles representing the individual cultures of the parties, while the overlapping area ought to provide for a “shared culture” in which communication takes place. The practical validity of such an approach is topic of debate. In later work it was recognised that culture does not simply act as a source of interference or ‘noise’ in communication, but can lead to complete misunderstanding about the most basic of presumptions (Avruch, 1998). In that approach, rather than envisaging an “overlapping” communication culture, a new culture is found to exist, that of “diplomacy”. This assumes that culture related communication problems are resolved between the ‘diplomats’ and their constituencies rather than between the ‘clashing’ cultures directly. The consequence is that a cultural “translation” becomes necessary, from each culture to the culture of “diplomacy”. A graphic representation of such a communication model is included in the figure below.

Figure 9 Diplomacy communication culture

Although this involves two ‘translations’ it evades the negative consequences of a direct confrontation. A parallel is to be found in dispute adjudication in the courts, where the parties no longer speak for themselves, but have to engage counsel to be able to present their case in this environment. It is interesting to note that the representatives are under a higher obligation to the court than to their respective clients. This follows from the situation that there is always another dispute to be resolved between other parties, and that it is therefore more important to maintain the integrity of the culture of dispute resolution system than that of the conflicting parties. Ultimately, the advocates must not be drawn into the cultural and emotional aspects of a conflict, and formal and informal rules to sustain a strong culture of the resolution environment itself are a means of avoiding that. The more formal resolution processes, in which procedural rules have increasing importance will therefore, have to maintain stronger cultures to enforce such formality.

The “common communication culture” approach is especially useful where more than two different cultures must be reconciled, in which case the amount of ‘translation’ effort is actually reduced.⁷²

It can be concluded that when dealing with parties from different cultural backgrounds, using a dispute resolution environment that ‘forces’ users to operate in a environment which is different from their own, but common to the conflict, would avoid problems related to cultural misunderstanding. It does however introduce another problem. It can be argued that it is impossible to really resolve a dispute in a setting where the parties’ culture has been removed from it. A dispute may be determined in such a context, but never resolved. In the New Zealand situation, the on-going problems with the final resolution of issues with the indigenous population provide a good example. Cultural differences may be of a procedural nature, but can also be of a fundamental nature. Staying with the example of the New Zealand indigenous population, the Maori culture provides for its own specific dispute resolution processes, but they have little significance or application outside the much broader concepts that underlie the Maori culture (Tomas & Quince, 1999). Resolving dispute by means of culturally defined mechanisms loses much of its relevance if the parties to a dispute do not share an understanding of the cultural environment in which these mechanisms operate.

The consequences of the cultural dimension for a CADR system as conceptualised in this paper are the recognition that cultural influences will impact the emotional bindings, the way relationship objects are perceived and even fundamental assumptions, such as concepts of property. The obvious fundamental differences will become apparent in the way the parties describe objects, and can be resolved at that point by proper translation into the legal concepts

⁷² As an example where five parties with different cultures are involved, a common communication culture would require five “translations”, while “translations” between the cultures would require ten. In formulaic form: $[(n \times (n-1)) / 2.]$

that govern the conflict resolution system (i.e. the law of the conflict). The cultural impact on emotional bindings can be compensated for, by analysing the way the parties' culture influences conflict behaviour. Much study is available in that area (Avruch, 1998), and practical instruments have been developed which can be used or adapted to "normalise" for cultural influences (Hofstede, 1984).⁷³ This can be conceptualised in much the same way as this was proposed under the analysis of conflict behaviour in a more general sense.⁷⁴ A questionnaire can be used that analyses cultural influences, and where significant differences are found between the parties, this analysis can be extended to the cultural impact on individual issues. Once the cultural impact has been given a measure for each party, this can be used to adjust the ratings of conflict issues between the parties. Further research and perhaps some practical tests will have to determine whether the cultural impact should be used independently or as an aspect of conflict behaviour. In one way or the other, cultural influences will play a role in the creation and composition of the emotional bindings (*B*).

4 *Culture and communication media*

In the context of this paper it is also relevant to consider the interaction between communication media and culture on conflict behaviour. A model of this interaction can be represented in the following diagram.

⁷³ Such cultural analysis often takes the form of a number of characteristics, for which values are determined between extremes. As an example, an adaptation of Hofstede's work (Sanders & Neuijen, 1987) uses dimensions such as process orientation v result orientation, human orientation v task orientation, organisation focus v professional focus, open v close, tight v loose control structures, pragmatism v normatism, central v distributed to analyse (in that case corporate) culture.

⁷⁴ As presented in chapter IV.F.

Figure 10 The influence of culture and communication media on negotiation⁷⁵

This model seeks to represent the concept that the “richness” of the communication media has an impact on the social cues that can be transmitted, thereby influencing the role of group and cultural influences on individual conflict behaviour. Using “lean” media⁷⁶, removes a significant proportion of visual and verbal cues, and therefore causes communicators to concentrate on message content and logical reasoning. If desired, that can be further enhanced by influencing the format in which messages can be exchanged, or even the content of messages. If a CADR system governs an exchange of information between parties, it can operate as a “filter” focussing the communication on certain characteristics, such as the substantive issues. This could be done by prescribing forms by which information is exchanged, and which simply do not allow for any emotive content to be expressed. Using strict language constraints, such as those proposed in this paper could serve such a purpose.

A second effect relates to interactivity of communication. Communication using a technical interface can be synchronous,

⁷⁵ (Barsness & Bhappu, 2004)

⁷⁶ Such as email or computer transmitted messages.

where parties can directly respond, and possibly intervene in the other's communication, or asynchronous where the messages are transferred with some time difference between them. Obviously, this is also something that can be manipulated where the communication environment is controlled. As an example, in a conflict with much emotional content, the communication system could impose a time-lag between receiving a message and allowing a reply, or could request confirmation of messages before they are transmitted etc.

D. THE PLACE OF OBJECTS IN THE MODEL.

The objects at issue are only indirectly represented. The model describes the conflict environment and dynamics, operating on the parties while dealing with the issues. In other words, the objects themselves and their determinants, such as descriptions and evidence are at a different abstraction level than that described by the conflict model. The model contains references to objects in the form of object states. In the resolution of conflict, evidence may be required of object states (*O*) and the related objectives (*Q*) and agents (*A*). That evidence will have been the basis of the description of the object states over time, and links to relevant documents and recorded statements will be readily available in the CADR system, because this is the way in which documents are introduced. The presence of object states in the model therefore implies the presence of evidence to support what has been registered. The objects themselves need not be represented in any detail in the models.

E. THE ROLE AND DETERMINATION OF OBJECTIVES

The proposition is that the conflict behaviour of a party at any point during the conflict is based on the influences as described through the parties' objectives. The purpose is to be able to analyse the emotional connections that are made with the substantive objects

in dispute. As has been seen, the objectives are described as the composition that results from an emotional binding and a certain object (or rather object state). The conglomerate of emotional bindings changes a simple transaction situation into one of conflict. In the CADR system, these emotional parameters will be recorded, and compared between the parties, and between their relations to substantive issues. In chapter V the formal theoretical basis of this analysis was described. It is proposed that this approach will eventually produce a 'map' of underlying interests, together with the relative importance of those interests, for each party separately, but also between the parties. This 'map' will provide the database from which to generate the simulation- and primary process functionality of the system. By mapping the emotional parameters at this level of detail, it is attempted to be able to describe conflict behaviour at various levels, and from different perspectives. Where existing conflict behaviour theory looks at the overall conflict behaviour, it is theorised that conflict behaviour will vary, both over time, and between the issues. If these conflict behaviour differences can be known, it will be possible to adapt a resolution strategy to the resulting matrix of substantive issues and their emotional relevance between the parties. The result is that the ranking of conflict issues, which is an important aspect of finding resolution alternatives, is not only based on the parties' input to it,⁷⁷ but can be supported by analytic detail based on the emotional binding determination at the level of individual issues.

⁷⁷ In the way for instance Kennedy suggests (Kennedy, 1998).

VII DYNAMIC MODEL OF CONFLICT

A satisfactory dynamic model of conflict has not been found. Therefore a number of existing theories and models have been combined and integrated. The resulting theory is represented in a model that is constructed using flow-chart techniques. The following model represents the recursive character of conflict dynamics, by introducing a number of 'loops' within its structure.

Figure 11 A dynamic conflict model.

A. *CONFLICT 'PHASES' IN THE DYNAMIC MODEL*

This concept, obtained from the various 'phase theories', is represented along the left vertical side of the diagram. It portrays the phases in a conflict as it develops. Simple phase theories recognise two phases (Walton, 1969). First differentiation, where the conflict escalates and the parties take increasingly opposite positions, and secondly integration, where the conflict reaches a point where further escalation is deemed useless and parties direct their attention to termination or resolution of the conflict. The expanded phase theories recognise additional phases of conflict development and resolution (Pondy, 1967; Rummel, 1976). The conflict phases can be seen to coincide with the different environments in which the conflict develops. This provides a second link between the static and dynamic models, with time being the most important connection.

1 *Latent phase*

The initial phase is represented by a "status quo". The parties have some relationship, resulting in interaction. This can be a long and complicated situation or a chance event, in which entirely unrelated parties become involved. An example of the first can be a business relationship, an example of the second a traffic accident.

More complicated or emotionally involved relationships in the latent phase generally result in increasingly complex and emotional conflicts. The underlying fact situation for a conflict is present, but no action is taken.

2 *Perceived or initiation phase*

The perceived phase starts with the realisation that differences have arisen, either over substantive issues or over relationship deficiencies. In this phase, conflict can still be avoided if the parties are motivated to communicate and resolve issues. A "trigger event"

terminates the perceived phase and starts the actual conflict escalation.

3 Balancing phase

The main recursive element is the “balancing” phase, in which the parties make their subsequent ‘moves’ as the conflict escalates. In the balancing phase the conflict is “internalised”, emotional bindings are created and communication is increasingly directed toward relationship and communication issues, rather than substantive issues. The term ‘balancing’ indicates the use of power and confrontation, and the evaluation that takes place after each party makes a move, and awaits the resulting counter move.

4 Resolution phase

A resolution (attempt) has characteristics of a balancing exercise, but takes place under different rules and in a different environment. It also represents a way out of the conflict. When successful, a resolution evaluation and aftermath phase is entered, and eventually the situation returns to a new status quo, in which a dispute is always “latent”. If the resolution attempt is unsuccessful the conflict returns to its ‘balancing’ phase.

5 Aftermath phase

The aftermath phase can be entered when one party avoids making further steps in the conflict escalation, and the other party accepts this avoidance. Such avoidance can have the characteristic of accepting a “loss”, but can also be a refusal to be engaged in conflict. The success of avoidance depends on the other party, which can accept avoidance (e.g. when this is perceived as ‘winning’), or decline to accept (e.g. when it is perceived as being ignored, or when some act is required from the avoiding party). Avoidance can be

seen as an attempt by one of the parties to return to a status quo without resolving the dispute (or bypassing the resolution phase). Non-acceptance by the other party is in that view a trigger event, immediately starting the balancing phase again.

The aftermath phase can also be entered through a resolution attempt. An unsuccessful resolution attempt will lead to the next step in the power balancing phase, while a successful attempt will bring about an evaluation, followed by transcending or encapsulating behaviour in the aftermath phase.

B. COMPONENTS OF THE DYNAMIC MODEL

1 Status quo

The status quo is strictly speaking not an element of a conflict model. The description is only used to provide a starting point for the dynamic representation, as well as an end point to which the situation can return when the conflict is terminated. As a result the status quo element contains no conflict information, but is used to store environmental data of a neutral character, describing the situation and relationship parameters before the conflict was triggered. In theory it must be possible for parties to describe and detail the information relating to the status quo element without generating new conflict issues. In practice this is hardly ever the case. Once the conflict situation has developed, the parties will do everything to ‘score points’. Even the description of perfectly neutral information will be influenced by conflict objectives, and will be coloured to reflect newly found “information” about the characteristics of the opponent. A system that is able to extract the information automatically from documents, and/or one in which the emotional components in objectives are analysed, and relationship objects are separated from substantive objects, will be useful in coming to a description of

the situation before the conflict arose that is free from post-conflict bias. This is helpful for both resolution and determination processes.

2 *Conflict perceived*

The ‘conflict perceived’ element is important, as it describes the conditions of the situation in which strictly speaking the conflict has not yet started (is not ‘expressed’), but all circumstances are in place for it to commence. All that is necessary for the conflict to ignite at this point is the ‘trigger event’. The ‘conflict perceived’ element can potentially play an interesting role in conflict resolution, as it describes a situation where the conflict parameters are present, but the situation is still in a ‘stable’ condition. It may be compared with the situation in a bomb, at the point where the timer has almost counted down to ‘zero’ (the typical movie situation in which the hero prevents ultimate disaster, with a few seconds to go).

Interestingly, as a result of emotional influences that arise as soon as the conflict is triggered, it is almost never possible to return to the conflict perceived situation and resolve the conflict from that perspective, which would be a desirable approach. As an example, a third party adjudication (i.e. arbitration or expert determination) could be used to resolve the “trigger” event only, after which a consensual (i.e. mediation process would remove the other latent issues). Unfortunately, the practical situation is normally that once the trigger event has taken place escalation occurs rapidly, and additional issues are introduced very quickly, resulting in an emotional contest that impedes such an attempt.

3 *Trigger event*

The trigger event can be an entirely insignificant occurrence or a major disruption. Generally speaking, complex and long lasting relationships tend to slowly grow into conflict and the trigger event

tends to be insignificant itself. Conflicts arising between relatively unrelated parties require trigger events with substantial impact. In conflict resolution, the description of the status quo and conflict perceived elements will indicate how much attention must be spent on the analysis of the trigger event. In relatively ‘empty’ status quo situations (unconnected parties) the analysis of the trigger event will be significant, while in ‘complicated’ status quo situations (where parties have complex relationships) the analysis of the conflict perceived situation is vital, and the trigger event will be insignificant in itself.

4 *Conflict engine*

The dashed line in the diagram encloses what is termed the conflict engine. This represents the part of the model where conflict interaction takes place, and the parties make their moves and counter-moves. Each step in this conflict escalation element represents a ‘snapshot’ of the static representation of the conflict.

(a) *Balancing*

The balancing element includes an evaluation by the parties on the available strategies, tactics and resources to make the next move. This element represents much of the effort that is put into the conflict by the parties. It includes the planning process involved in contemplating the effects of the last move of the opponent, and considering the own next move. The opponents’ moves are analysed and perceptions are generated as to the underlying motives. Resources are evaluated and advisors consulted. As a result, emotional bindings are formed and adjusted. Objectives are evaluated and adjusted. The conflict strategy (which can be represented as the sum of all goal objectives, ΣQ^G) may be discussed with the reference group

(A^{Rg}), and the next move is contemplated and prepared. Goal objectives (Q^G) are evaluated and adjusted.

(b) Move

A move requires a statement (Q^S), possibly combined with an action (Q^D) representing a change in an object state (O'). It is not necessary to define a minimum level of activity that would amount to a step. By simply recording all action- and statement-objectives individually, the conflict development can be analysed at any level of detail.

(c) Evaluate

After each move a party evaluates the immediate results of its move and decides to avoid further conflict, to escalate, or to attempt resolution. Similarly, the other party considers the effect of the last move by its opponent and makes the same decision.

(d) Escalate

If the choice is to escalate, typically further demands will be made or firmer positions taken. The parties 'dig in', which has been called "increase inflexibility". The situation returns to the balancing element.

5 Resolution and integration

Resolution events are part of a conflict. It is important to note that the reverse proposition is not logically correct, quite opposite, resolution attempts are typically organised to take place 'outside' the conflict, by limiting conflict behaviour, although this is often unsuccessful. It is proposed that an incorrect perception within the ADR profession is that it is involved in 'conflict resolution'; just as it is incorrect to say that a medical professional's interference would 'heal' someone. The best that any doctor, and for that matter, any

ADR practitioner, can achieve is to create circumstances in which healing can take place, by removing or suppressing distorting conditions. It is therefore necessary to see resolution as a part of a dynamic conflict model, in which an attempt is made to bring an end to the escalation or continuation of the conflict.

Given that most resolution attempts are confidential, it is unlikely that anything else will be recorded than the fact of a resolution attempt and its results on object states, in case the dispute is not resolved. Non resolution can lead to significant effects on emotions, both positive and negative.

6 *Evaluation*

Once a resolution attempt has been completed, and the conflict is not continued, the situation can return to a status quo directly, i.e. where the dispute is one in an ongoing business relationship. In most conflicts however, an additional step is necessary, which represents the way a party deals with the outcome psychologically. This takes place in the “aftermath” stage.

7 *The conflict aftermath*

At the moment three options are proposed. A party can unilaterally use only one of these, namely avoidance. It can be argued that avoidance is not really a conflict aftermath process, but a type of conflict behaviour. The result of avoidance, when “accepted” by the other party, is that the conflict is terminated. Therefore the avoidance element is placed in the aftermath phase. The other two aftermath elements follow from a completed resolution process, and represent the ways a party deals with its outcome.

The aftermath phase is not very relevant for the purpose of this paper, and is dealt with very briefly.

(a) *Avoidance*

As said, there can be argument if this is really an aftermath element.

(b) *Transcend*

A party is said to transcend a conflict outcome when the result is accepted and the party “gets on with life”. The situation returns to a status quo in which there may, or may not be further dealings with the opponent. A new trigger event would be necessary to start another conflict cycle.

(c) *Encapsulate*

This represents a much more difficult process. It is one in which the outcome is not readily accepted and not ‘internalised’. The outcome must be psychologically ‘encased’, and will remain a source for negative emotions.

VIII THE CADR SYSTEM CONCEPT

A. INTRODUCTION

The CADR system will require parties to analyse their dispute when entering information relating to the issues. The system will provide tools to assist the parties, or their advisors, with this task. At this point no clear idea exists what format such tools will have, but it is not too difficult to conceptualise how objectives description will take place. The system should “force” the user to break objectives up into the smallest possible units, and each resulting objective (*Q*) in its related object state description (*O*) and binding (*B*). The resulting database of object states, and related objectives will be used to provide the building blocks from which an objective conflict narrative can be constructed. The registration of time in each element will make it possible to create chronologies that will help checking the logic of any narrative that is constructed. Because the system will be able to present the data from various perspectives (e.g. time, objectives, agent, statement v goals, action v statements etc) it will be possible to check for inconsistencies, and to determine the relevance of documents and statements. From a user’s perspective the system will have similarities to an advanced litigation support system, but with much more detail. Events are registered, and are related to documents and conflict issues. The registration of perceived objectives of the opponent and analysis of emotional bindings are a major difference with litigation support systems. The most important difference however, is that the CADR system is primarily a communication tool, not something to assist in presenting one side of a conflict in the most persuasive manner.

B. ISSUE DISTILLATION

The part of the system that will perform this function has conceptually been termed the ‘issue distiller’. The models and concepts produced in this first phase of the project will be used to define and construct this tool. Meta-data extraction tools or tools that analyse text to retrieve concepts and related terminology could provide a platform on which an issue distiller can be constructed. The main problems to overcome are the completion of the conflict language syntax and construction of a relevant ontology. The next problem would be the definition of an interface, which is suitable for disputants, their adviser and neutrals alike.

It is not likely that an “issue distiller” would operate entirely automatic, but such a tool can apply semantic analysis and retrieve concepts, which can be “fed back” to the user of the system to assist in formulating and describing the individual issues and their relationships. The “vortex” character of conflict has been described, which results in an increase of issues as conflict develops. It is hypothesised that ‘concepts’ that will be retrieved by semantic analysis will correlate with the conflict objects (*O*). As these are the focus of the objectives (*Q*), and as time is a recorded parameter, it must be possible to present the user with a chronology which will assist in describing the development of the conflict in a more analytical way. As an example, parties that have been in a conflict situation for some time tend to merge all the issues and their emotional impact. By showing that certain objectives (*Q*) have developed in different stages of the conflict, the issues may be prised apart, and considered on their own merits, which increases the chances of resolution.

C. ISSUE STATEMENT DESCRIPTION

There will need to be an “issue statement descriptor”, which is essentially a reframing tool. This is the part of the system where a

neutral (or possibly counsel) can potentially assist the party in describing their issues in such a manner that they become resolvable. In the mediation context this is sometimes referred to as asking “why” questions. In this phase the links to underlying documentation and reference to evidential material will have to be completed, and the system will have to provide for a classification system of such evidence. Obviously, the system will need interfaces to document management systems to perform this task, although it is envisaged that most of that will be able to be accomplished using standard web-technology. This sub-system will eventually be used for the purpose of discovery and other formalised information exchange functions.⁷⁸ Various confidentiality levels will need to be introduced as well, providing the possibility to frame a ‘resolution process strategy’, which involves the gradual disclosure of information about emotional bindings and non-disclosed objectives.⁷⁹

D. EMOTIONAL BINDING ANALYSIS

In this module the emotional bindings will be extracted and recorded. By using automated questionnaires and semantic analysis, the strengths of emotions in relation to each issue are determined, while at the same time an analysis is made of the impact of stakeholders on the issues and emotional bindings. As an example, once the issues are determined a user can be asked to rank the issues in the order of importance, or value them in some way. Lists of words can be presented from which choices are made to determine the strength of emotional relationships. By asking how a party thinks a stakeholder would rate the issues, or how the other party would rate is-

⁷⁸ The proposed new District Court rules for New Zealand provide a parallel in the form of “information capsules”, which are essentially a collection of evidential and descriptive material, which the parties are obliged to exchange in the period leading up to a compulsory “consensual” settlement conference.

⁷⁹ Which may be compared with the use of privilege in formal resolution processes.

sues, information can be gathered about the impact of perceptions, or the influence of stakeholders.⁸⁰ Also, the impact of cultural components can be investigated. The concept is that emotional bindings find their origin in a number of unrelated factors such as economical importance, impact on family situations, perception of ‘self’ etc, which cannot be easily determined or evaluated. By using the intermediate step of emotional binding analysis, a communication process can be started without requiring the parties to disclose at that stage exactly why such emotional values attach to substantive issues (if they would be able to recognise that in the first place). This will become relevant later, when the basis of emotional bindings will have to be analysed. The emotional binding analysis must therefore include details that remain confidential to the parties, but which will help each party to understand how its own position is constructed (This could be referred to as assisting in the determination of one’s BATNA, the best alternative to a negotiated outcome (Fisher *et al.*, 1991). An important element of BATNA establishment is reality testing, which is used to adjust emotional bindings (*B*) and related object states (*O*’). It is conceivable that a very advanced system would be able to analyse each substantive issue automatically once it has been identified, and retrieve relevant existing case law to assist in this process.⁸¹

⁸⁰ Interesting research in this area (Brabers & Kooistra, 1975), used a simple electronic instrument to record and compare two parties’ (bivalent) opinions about a statement. Each party was asked to give the opinion from its own, but also from the other’s perspective, and the results are compared. For an introduction to the technique of priority ranking, and the use of such rankings in negotiation see Kennedy (Kennedy, 1998).

⁸¹ Research is currently conducted which approaches that type of functionality for liability disputes. See <http://cedire.org/>, the “BEST-project”, which stands for Batna Establishment using Semantic Techniques. The aim of that project is to use semantic analysis to find case law that is relevant to a specific fact situation. An advanced system as alluded to here would require that the structures and concepts of law are reduced to a formal language, with a hierarchical syntax, and extensive database of terms, each connected with “ordinary” words for these terms, in a thesaurus-like structure. This may be less complicated as it seems, especially when it is considered that the vast majority of disputes resolves around relatively simply legal situations, made complicated by the emotional issues.

E. INITIAL INFORMATION EXCHANGE

Up to some point the system operates for the parties individually, followed by stages where information is exchanged and compared, and conclusions are drawn. The first and most important step is the exchange of the “reduced” issues. As each party has been forced to analyse its own version of events, this exchange will probably be quite revealing. The ultimate aim of this exchange of information process is to get the parties to agree on a comprehensive list of issues. During this process information on each side must be updated, eventually generating an amended set of issues with attached values and emotional bindings on each side. In this stage an overlap between issues and evidence will arise. Issues are of course coloured by opinions, positions and interests, and evidential matters will become apparent.

F. SUBSTANTIVE ISSUE VALUATION AND COMPARATIVE EVALUATION

The substantive issue valuation is the first module in which parties’ databases are compared. By comparing the relative values attached to the issues, a party’s grading can be “weighted” before it is compared with those of the other party. The result of this process will generate the first ideas on which direction a resolution may take. Some examples demonstrate how that might work.

- Goal objectives related to substantive objects (Q^{GOM}) that are compatible (<c>), or almost compatible (<~c>), while the related statement objectives (Q^{SOM}), are not (<nc>), will provide issues where the system can suggest settlement terms.
- Goal objectives (Q^G) that are incompatible (<nc>) but have very different priority rankings (which can be established by the related emotion value (m) in their binding (B), or by means of the difference between the object state values (O') of the related Q^S and Q^G , will be those most suitable for bargaining.

- Goal objectives (Q^G) that have a related object state (O') which differs marginally from the actual object state for that object, but which are nevertheless in dispute, are suitable candidates for substantive negotiation gestures, or for bargaining.
- Issues over objects with large differences in the perceived goal objectives of the other party (Q_{A2}^{G1}) and actual goal objectives of that party (Q_{A2}^G), are candidates for resolution by information exchange.

G. EMOTIONAL BINDING VALUATION AND COMPARATIVE EVALUATION

The next comparison is more complicated as it involves the weighting of the emotional bindings, and the influence of stakeholders and conflict behaviour. At this point the emotional bindings will have to be disclosed, which is a process that will be undertaken in stages. Bindings that rely on objectively determinable issues will be easier to evaluate than legal positions, which will be easier than peer-group influences or entirely irrational motivations or those entirely based on the use of power. The purpose of a gradual process starting at objective-, and working towards entirely subjective arguments is to allow the parties to accept a satisfactory outcome as soon as this arises, and before disclosure of all underlying emotions and intentions has taken place. This approach can leave the trade-off process between more or less comparable values in control of the parties themselves for as long as possible, and thereby creates an empowering environment.

Again, some examples can be provided.

- It is at this point relevant to analyse entitlement or rights-issues as those are included in the emotional bindings that the parties have attached to the substantive issues. Differences in the motivation elements (m) of the bindings (B), at the level of individual objects will indicate which issues can possibly be resolved with better information exchange.

- Issues where the emotional values of the parties are very different, but the related object states are not too far apart $\left(Q_{A_1} < nc > Q_{A_2} ; O'_{(A_1)} < \approx c > O'_{(A_2)} \right)$ will be those that can be used for ‘face-saving’ gestures, which can improve the emotional setting of the conflict.
- Significant cultural influences on the emotional bindings will indicate the issues that will be difficult to resolve.
- Significant peer group influences on bindings will indicate issues that will require some form of “emotional” trade off. The system will be able to indicate which issues are suitable for such a trade off, by comparing peer group influences and perceived versus actual goals.
- By comparing intention values (n) in the bindings (B), issues may be selected that are suitable for a quick, integrative resolution. These can be used by a mediator as an “example” that a cooperative approach works.

The emotional binding analysis also has a retrospective character. Previous ‘moves’ will be analysed, because the system will request information to populate the database underlying the objectives (Q) analysis. As a result a party will have to think about its own motivations behind these objectives when they were executed, and will be confronted with any inconsistencies that arise. As an example, a party may be asked to retrospectively provide motives for past objectives, which may be compared with current motives, related to objectives that are contemplated. Any differences, especially where these relate to the same object, will have arisen as a result of, or at least influenced by, the conflict situation. Such an analysis may help the party to think about the way the conflict has influenced its objectives.

A novel way of using the emotional binding analysis would be to have each party assess the way it thinks the other party perceives

its objectives and the emotional binding components behind these objectives. A party would thereby be asked to effectively create the narrative for the other party. The system could provide a means for those narratives to be exchanged, whereby each party can then 'correct' the other parties' version of its own objectives. This could result in a communication between the parties about why they have certain objectives, in other words, communication about interests, and not about positions (Fisher *et al.*, 1991; Lewicki *et al.*, 2001).

H. INFORMATION STORAGE OBJECTIVES

The CADR system will eventually include all the relevant data in relation to the dispute, and it will therefore be useful in case the dispute is later arbitrated or litigated. The system will be forcing the parties to contemplate their dispute and consider its origins and development. This process itself may be conducive to an early resolution. A second advantage of this compulsory entering of dispute information is that it provides the opportunity to explain the resolution process at the same time. This may prove an important educational function of the CADR system. The average disputant will not be aware that there is a large amount of information available how conflict operates, and how the behaviour of both parties is determinative of the way a conflict develops, and is eventually resolved. By providing relevant information in the course of using the CADR system, it may be possible to change behaviour towards more integrative styles, thereby increasing the chance of resolution, or at least decreasing the chance of further escalation.

The end result of both parties completing the data-entry and analysis process will be:

- An electronic repository of all relevant documents and statements made by the parties, indexed and referenced to the issues in conflict, and to each other. (replacing a common bundle, with much better accessibility)

- A database describing these documents including relevant meta-data, which would include the evidential status of each document, or argument about that. (replacing lists of documents)
- A database containing information on agent and object states over time, and information on the different objectives over time, including perceived objectives. (a chronology of events, but ‘on steroids’)
- A narrative by each party, referenced to the data bases, and made up of a sequence of events, correlating with the documents. (briefs of evidence)
- A joint narrative, generated with the aid of the system, and which is based on non-disputed facts. (a statement of agreed facts)

It is envisaged that the end result of the issue entering process alone is an agreed list of substantive issues, each broken down to its smallest possible component. For each party there will be a list of evidential material, referred to the substantive issues, and categorised in different disclosure and confidentiality levels. A separate body of information is an argument database, containing the parties’ opinions and statements in relation to the substantive issues. Separated in another collection are the information on the relative importance of the substantive issues, and the information on the emotional bindings. The emotional binding information contains overall information on relevant cultural and group influence characteristics. Some of this information is strictly restricted to the individual parties, while most of it will have various “exchange levels” which can be changed by the parties themselves (following suggestions from the system, advisors, or the neutral).

I. SYSTEM OUTPUT

At this point the system should provide functionality to produce lists of documents, issue description documents, reports on relative importance of issues, financial information etc.

It must be noted that the parties will have a much better understanding of their own dispute than they typically now have when entering into dispute resolution processes. Much communication will have taken place between the parties, but always through the system, and focussed on substantive issues. Much irrelevant material will have been discarded along the way.

J. RESOLUTION SUPPORT

It is conceptualised that the next stages of the use of the system are investigations into possible solution ‘matrices’ based on the ranking of substantive issues, using the relative importance and emotional values of those issues. These solution matrices can be generated by the system or by the neutral using it. An important role for the neutral is to analyse the data and locate ‘bottlenecks’ in the generation of alternative matrices. The system should be helpful, by indicating which issues frustrate the construction of resolution matrices. The neutral can then address such specific issues with the parties, and see if agreement can be reached on adjusting the relative importance or emotional bindings on such issues, to remove obstacles to the generation of more possible solutions.

Another way of assisting resolution would be to analyse with the parties what the relative strength of arguments is by inviting them to increase disclosure of relevant background information. This approach is different from the preceding one in that it results in adjusting of values and bindings as a result of reasoning, and not a negotiation process.

A third way of assisting resolution is to evaluate the legal concepts behind the various issues. Obviously this would require assistance from a legal professional, but suggestions could be made to obtain an opinion on individual issues, which again would lead to adjusting values and bindings. This involves the mediation tech-

nique of “reality testing”, whereby the relative strength of a party’s position is evaluated.

This description is obviously very abstract and premature, but it describes the direction in which development of the models has taken place.

IX APPENDICES

A. LITIGATION SUPPORT SYSTEMS

An area of development in information systems relating to conflict is that of litigation support. The first time such a system was documented to be used was in the early seventies in a court case that had IBM as one of the parties and involved thousands of documents. This is where these systems have originally been focussed at, the handling of large volumes of written material (Baker, 2003). With the advance of OCR (optical character recognition) and automated text searching these tools have become more powerful and can now conveniently retrieve not only text, but also sound, video and other images. Especially in the US these developments have taken on a life of their own, and specialist companies provide advanced litigation support services based on complex systems.

A somewhat different development is that of case analysis systems, which operate additionally to the traditional litigation support systems. These systems are used to analyse the fact situations making up a case, and link these to the evidential information in the documents. Additional modules are used to create chronologies and graphical representation of these, a variety of lists and overviews to exchange information with clients and other members of the legal team. The typical organisation of these systems has four perspectives: facts, persons, issues and evidence. The facts are analysed by looking at exchange of information or events between personalities, and are linked to the evidential material, supporting this version of events and categorised in legal issues. Each event receives a rating on how it supports the legal position on each issue. These systems are primarily aimed at litigation, and at winning a case in an adversarial court setting, although of course the structural way of analys-

ing a party's position, can also be helpful in settlement negotiations or even mediation. The basic structure of registration of events and communication between parties and related documents follows directly from the communication model that underlies conflict, and which is also used in this paper.

These systems are however, not set up to support communication between parties, which is the starting assumption for the CADR system. There are sufficient similarities to look at the concepts behind litigation support systems to define some of the functionality of the ADR system.

B. DISPUTE RESOLUTION SYSTEMS

Folger et al (2005) describe a negotiation support system. This system is used as 'intelligent' whiteboard, by providing tools to list and categorise issues, and to attach rankings to them for different aspects (e.g. desirability versus feasibility). Various graphical representations are possible, and by using a central large screen, and connected individual computers for each participant, different voting mechanisms are possible. They comment that using such a system assists in communication and focussing on the issues. A perceived disadvantage is the lack of focus on emotional issues. A third party facilitator assists in operating this infrastructure and issue analysis. The system itself does not contain "intelligence" with regards to such analysis.

An upcoming field is that of ODR, which stands for online dispute resolution. These are typically message based communication systems that are used to resolve disputes arising out of e-transaction and internet auction transactions. They typically operate in environments where it is not practical that other systems are used.

Another area in which much development takes place, and where a number of well established providers are operating, is in

online settlement systems. These are sites where negotiating parties can enter a number of “final bids” and where relatively simple algorithms determine a settlement amount, when these final bids overlap. These sites are very successful, as they help in avoiding the posturing that normally takes place in negotiation and provide the parties with a non-personal environment to conduct final negotiations. These services are typically used in settling insurance claims etc. They process enormous amounts of procedures.

A study undertaken in 2003, found 76 online dispute resolution sites worldwide (Conley Tyler *et al.*, 2003). Various types of dispute resolution processes are offered, but the only types that are truly automated are the facilitated negotiation procedures, which are essentially a form of “blind bidding”, as described above. The sites that provide more complex procedures mostly comprise of an access “portal” to more traditional services, although these are offered on a “remote” basis, where the neutral engages with the parties by means of email exchange or “chat” environments, or in the more advanced cases by more direct means, such as video conferencing.

Good examples of this type of ODR are the various services that are provided for the resolution of domain name disputes. Thousands of cases are handled effectively in this environment, simply by using the efficient means of communication that is provided by the World Wide Web. This efficiency is assisted by the fact that domain names are assigned by a relatively small number of organisations who can prescribe in great detail how conflicts are resolved, because they have the ultimate authority in the use of domain names.

Complaint handling is another example, where large organisations bring their complaint departments on-line, or where services are provided for the users of on-line trading and auction sites.

An upcoming trend appears to be case appraisal, where legally qualified individuals provide information about the legal merits of a

conflict situation, which is presented to them by either one or both parties to a dispute. This would be akin to obtaining legal advice in the traditional way, but increased in efficiency by the use of modern communication technology.

In some jurisdictions, the Courts themselves are developing systems, by which litigation can be started, and in which much of the formalities and document exchange between the parties and the Court is organised.⁸² In the United States such systems are made available by commercial organisations, working in cooperation with the Courts.

The author has not found systems with the scope of the CADR system as proposed in this paper.

⁸² For an example see www.courtservice.gov.uk/mcol/

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